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D4.1: Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions

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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Executive summary

One of the core goals of Project O is to demonstrate the efficacy of adopting water reuse technologies to shift towards a circular economy for long-term, sustainable water management. While globally water reuse is of great interest to contrast the projected increase in global and local water demands, water loops have the potential to become an essential component of integrated water management strategies in water-stressed regions. Project O Work Package 4 targets the design, development, and testing of an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management strategies and water reuse technologies. This deliverable D4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions) illustrates the output of the activities carried out in Task 4.1 (Multi-objective water planning portfolios design) for Demo site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP) system, Italy.

AQP is one of the largest water distribution systems in Europe and is located in one of the driest areas. The aqueduct network has an extension of 20,000 kilometres, 30 times the length of the Po River, and a transport capacity of over 790 million cubic meters of water every year to ensure drinking water supply to over 4.5 million people. Covering an area of 19,541 km², Apulia is the fifth Italian region in terms of irrigated area and has the highest number of agricultural workers. Agriculture has a central role in the regional economy, and the exposure of community welfare to drought is a major challenge. As shown by our analysis, in recent years, sequential droughts have overstressed the system forcing, in some cases, to water supply curtailments. In this context, the adoption of water reuse technologies can increase water availability and enhance supply reliability, bringing better preparedness for emergencies.

The DAP developed for the AQP system is composed of the following components: i) candidate water portfolios (i.e. combinations of traditional water management options and new water reuse technologies); ii) evaluation indicators to assess - in a multidimensional fashion - the impact of the different portfolios (e.g., cost, water deficit); iii) a mathematical model of the AQP system to simulate the behaviour of the entire water system for the different portfolios under present and future climate and socio-economic scenarios; iv) a multi-objective optimisation engine to select Pareto efficient portfolios; and v) a computationally efficient model reduction of a subpart of the AQP water system (the water distribution network) to make the simulation-based optimisation of water portfolios computationally feasible within the life of the project.

In T4.1, we developed all the above components for the baseline scenario (current water demand and hydroclimatic conditions) and ran a set of optimisation experiments to retrieve Pareto efficient water portfolios. Specifically, we considered alternative water portfolios composed of the following options: a) operating policy for each of the five reservoirs feeding the AQP system and operated by the Irrigation Districts; b) water diversion policy for the diversion dams feeding irrigation and industrial districts and operated by the Irrigation Districts; c) percentage of water reuse, based on the capacity of water treatment and recycling technologies; d) distribution and supply capacity expansion system as the construction of a new canal and the activation of non-conventional sources such as abandoned wells that would not be usually integrated into the system. As T4.1 concerns the baseline (current) scenarios only, options c) and d) are here only formally introduced while they will be analysed in T4.4 as a potential solution to cope with future climate and socio-economic scenarios.

Water portfolios have been assessed through a set of indicators, including 1) water reuse cost, which refers to the cost of the treatment technology; 2) operating cost of the distribution network as dictated by the energy price (e.g., for pumping and treatment); 3) water supply deficit for farmers, urban drinking water and industry measured as the quadratic difference between supply and demand. The whole AQP water system (strategic model) model has been coded in C++ and calibrated/validated using available observational data. A reduced-order model of the water distribution model (Aquator) currently operated by AQPspa has been developed in the form of a non-linear response surface mapping the inputs (e.g., inflow, precipitation, evaporation, demands, etc.) to the water volume distributed to each one of the demand points in the water distribution network and couple with the strategic model. The multi-objective evolutionary algorithms BORG has been adopted to generate a set of Pareto-optimal portfolios via repeated simulations of the strategic model. The resulting portfolios represent the trade-offs across the evaluation indicators under current water demand and hydroclimatic scenarios.

Seasonally variable variations in the drinking supply deficit are observed, in particular with the highest values during the summer when demand increases due to tourist flows and competition with irrigation is greater. As regards the cost of purification, the differences between the various simulated years are minimal, less than 2%, mainly due to a different exploitation of the groundwater, as the relative pumping costs are among the most significant.

The volume stored in the five strategic reservoirs considered has a very homogeneous trend, with the typical recharge curve starting from November and ending in March, and the emptying starting between May and June until reaching a minimum in October. Faced with such a similar trend, the irrigation supply deficits in the respective districts served show a certain variability, with the worst years generally concentrated in the last years of the horizon considered.

Acronyms and abbreviations

ANN:	Artificial Neural Network
AQP:	Acquedotto Pugliese
ARPA:	Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Ambientale (Regional Agency for Environmental Protection)
COM:	Component Object Model
DAF:	Decision Analytics Framework
DAP:	Decision Analytics Platform
DM:	Decision-Maker
DP:	Dynamic Programming
DPS:	Direct Policy Search
ECMWF:	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EFAS:	European Flood Awareness System
EIPLI:	Ente per lo sviluppo dell'Irrigazione e la trasformazione fondiaria in Puglia, Lucania e Irpinia (Organization for the development of irrigation and land transformation in Puglia, Lucania and Irpinia)
EM-DAT:	Emergency Events Database
EMODPS:	Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search
FAO:	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GIS:	Geographic Information System
ICT:	Information and Communication Technologies
ID:	Irrigation District
ISPRA:	Istituto superiore per la protezione e la ricerca ambientale (Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research)
MOEA:	Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm
RBF:	Radial Basis Function
SDP:	Stochastic Dynamic Programming
SH:	Stakeholder
VBA:	Visual Basic® for Applications
WMO:	World Meteorological Organization
WP:	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This document is the Deliverable D4.1 – *Multi-objective water planning portfolios design under baseline conditions*, part of Work Package 4 activities undertaken in Task T4.1 - *Multi-objective water planning portfolios design*, aimed at producing of a set of optimally designed water planning portfolios and at evaluating associated performance with respect to a multidimensional assessment space.

The goal of WP4 is to design, develop, and test an ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy-makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, i.e. combinations of traditional water management options and new water reuse technologies, under current and projected water availability and demand conditions. The workflow of WP4 is illustrated in Figure 1: a set of candidate portfolios is first identified in collaboration with local stakeholders, including the local water supply company, water management bodies, and the water authorities. These are evaluated through a simulation-based optimization with respect to a set of indicators (e.g., cost, reliability) under current climate and socio-economic conditions (baseline scenarios) in order to select a subset of portfolios of potential interest for policy-makers (technically Pareto efficient portfolios). The efficient portfolios are further screened in Task T4.3 against a variety of future scenarios to retrieve the most robust ones, i.e., those better performing in the worst conditions. We will refer to the integration of these mathematical modelling components as a Decision Analytic Framework (DAF). The DAF is complemented in T4.2 with visual

Figure 1: The WP4 workflow.

analytics tools to form the ICT-based DAP that will support the in-depth trade-off analysis of water portfolios by policy-makers.

The DAF is composed of a water system model coupled with an optimisation engine. The water system model conceptualises the main natural processes and human decisions at the whole river basin scale and balances accuracy in process characterisation and reduced computational requirements to allow the simulation-based optimisation of the water portfolios. Such optimisation is performed using multi-objective evolutionary algorithms (MOEAs, for a review, see Maier et al., 2014), which generate a set of Pareto-optimal solutions representing the trade-offs across the design indicators. Technically, a portfolio is defined as Pareto-optimal (or nondominated) if no other solution gives a better value for one indicator without degrading the performance in at least one other indicator. The image in the indicator space of the Pareto-optimal solutions is the Pareto front. The advantage of this a-posteriori approach with respect to traditional a-priori methods, such as cost-benefit analysis or multi-attribute value theory, is that decision-makers do not have to state what is preferred in the absence of their understanding of what is attainable (Cohon and Marks, 1975).

In addition, it allows considering heterogeneous and incommensurable utility functions without going through any monetisation process. Finally, MOEAs jointly optimise the planning (i.e. new water loops) and the management (i.e. water infrastructure operations) components of water portfolios. The operations of water infrastructure are based on standard information (i.e. day of the year, storage in each reservoir) and by ad-hoc indices capturing the presence, the intensity, and the evolution of droughts.

The report is structured as follows: the next chapter illustrates the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct and provides an overview of existing data and models; Chapter 3 describes the main components of the DAF; Chapter 4 is devoted to the water system model identification (structure, calibration, and validation); experiment setting and numerical results are reported in Chapter 5, while Chapters 6 summarise the main takeaways of T4.1. In the end, an appendix on the drought characterisation.

2 The Italian demo site: Apulian Aqueduct

2.1 System Description

The Decision Analytics Platform (DAP) is demonstrated on Demo site 1, the case study of the Apulian Aqueduct (AQP), located in the Apulia Region, Italy. In this section, we will illustrate the case study, describe the data used to build the baseline scenario, report an extensive drought analysis, and describe the Aquator model currently used by the AQP water utility (AQPspa) for the operation of the water distribution network.

2.1.1 Apulia Region

The Apulia Region is an area of 19,541 km² located in South Italy and characterised by a Mediterranean climate with hot and dry summers and mild winters. During summer, precipitations are scarce may be missing for months. During winter, rainfalls are limited by the Southern Apennines with respect to the Atlantic depressions; here, rainfalls are shaped by the Mediterranean rising perturbation raids or by the cold air from the north or north-east (Ronco et al., 2017). Apulia is a very vast and differentiated area, mostly articulated in mainland and two peninsulas, the Salento in the south, projecting into the Gulf of Taranto and representing the south-eastern extremity of Italy, and the Gargano Promontory, which is a mountainous part of the region, consisting of the external Apennine thrust belt. The region is characterised by the karstic substrate's high permeability that favours rainwater infiltration. Consequently, there are few surface rivers concentrated in the northern area: Candelaro, Cervaro, Carapelle, Ofanto, while Fortore and Bradano river basins rely on the northern and western boundaries across the Molise and Basilicata regions, respectively (Ronco et al., 2017).

Despite low annual rainfall, scarce endogenous water, and a small hydrographic network, agriculture is a very developed sector in Apulia, mostly based on intensive olive growing, viticulture, and horticulture. As a result, Apulia is the fifth Italian region in terms of irrigated area and volumes of irrigation water used (Sardaro et al., 2018). Apulia has the highest number of agricultural workers among the Italian Regions, and this reveals the tremendous impact that agriculture has, especially on the regional economy and community welfare (Sardaro et al., 2016). More than 80% of the Apulian surface is currently used for agricultural purposes, and about 10% is covered by wild vegetation (Corine Land Cover, 2018¹). The largest part of agricultural land is devoted to arable crops (mainly cereals). Still, the most profitable part is the one related to olives (32%), vineyards (9%), citrus (3%), and vegetables (2%) productions (Ronco et al., 2017). These considerations make the economic dependence of this Region on agricultural yield even more evident. Given the scarcity of surface water, Apulian aquifers were a valuable water source in terms of quality and quantity in the past, hence extremely important to agriculture. These resources have been increasingly exploited since the early decades of the last century. To date, despite scientific, technical, and cultural progress, management and governance policies couldn't avoid the gradual depletion of these limited resources (Polemio et al., 2009).

The Apulian territory is divided into Irrigation Districts (ConSORZI di Bonifica) storing, supplying, and distributing water to farmers through irrigation networks and covering 90% (Lamaddalena et al., 2004) of the Region surface, as shown in Figure 2. An Irrigation District is an Italian public legal authority that takes care of the operation and maintenance of public reclamation works. In addition, it monitors privates' activities in the area of competence, manages hydraulic security, and operates reservoirs and irrigation water systems.

Apulia counts six Irrigation Districts that are different for dimensions, climate, and crops. Hereafter they are presented with their extension:

- Consorzio di Bonifica di Arneo - 252,981 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Capitanata - 441,545 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Gargano - 150,337 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Stornara e Tara - 142,949 ha
- Consorzio di Bonifica di Terre d'Apulia - 569,807ha

¹ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

- Consorzio di Bonifica di Ugento Li Foggi - 189,494 ha.

Figure 2: Apulian Region Irrigation Districts.

2.1.2 Apulian water system

To provide water to the seven Irrigation Districts and other water users all over the Region, a vast and complex network of pipes and canals has been built. The adduction system has been developing for one century by successive additions to the main canal, named “Canale Principale”, crossing from North to South the whole region and conveying spring water to towns and cities. The hydro-morphological features of the Apulia Region, which impede the stock of large volume of surface waters, required the development of large interregional water transfer schemes, collecting water flowing from surrounding Regions (Basilicata, Campania, Calabria, and Molise), to meet the Apulian water demand (Ronco et al., 2017). Overall, the system now features five major reservoirs: Occhito (on the Fortore river), Locone (on the homonymous creek), Conza (on the Ofanto river), Monte Cotugno (on the Sinni River), and Pertusillo (on the Agri River), as well as the Sele-Calore springs (Caposele), and several wells. It is important to notice that this territory is part of Appennino Meridionale Water Authority, which has an overall sufficient water availability but is not evenly distributed. There is thus the need of transferring the resource from confining regions and for long distances.

The main adduction and distribution scheme in the Apulia Region, is managed by Acquedotto Pugliese S.p.A. (AQPspa²). AQP is one of the largest and oldest European water utilities, operating in this area for over a century. To provide drinking and irrigation water to the entire Region, one of the world's most extended adduction systems (around 5000 km) has been built. The main supply network is structured in six water conveyance schemes: Sele-Calore, Pertusillo, Sinni, Fortore, Locone, Ofanto, distributed across four regions and all interconnected to transfer water from one scheme to the other (see Figure 3).

² <https://www.aqp.it/>

Figure 3: AQP network with main canals and water sources (reservoirs and natural spring - triangles).

Nowadays, AQPspa manages a water network of 21,000 km (30 times the length of the Po River), including the urban distribution networks, about 11,000 km of sewerage networks, and 184 treatment plants. More than half of the network was built before 1970 and requires continuous maintenance and modernisation (Balacco et al., 2017). When failures in water supply occur during the irrigation phase, crops are exposed to risk, and farmers resort to private wells to guarantee the amount of water needed.

Table 1 reports data from “Autorità di Bacino Regione Puglia, Relazione Finale Vol. 1 – Il Comparto Agricolo Pugliese (ABRP1)” representing the average volumes of water distributed from each Consortium with the associated source of supply.

Table 1: Average Water Distribution

Irrigation District	Source of supply	Supplied water [Cubic meters/year]	Total Supplied water [Cubic meters/year]
Arneo	Wells	498373	498373
Capitanata	Occhito Reservoir	63058333	100264712
	Ofanto River	10914123	
	Marana Capacciotti	26292256	
Gargano	Springs	178099	185566
	Wells	8467	
Stornara e Tara	Monte Cotugno Reservoir	23098127	39755333
	San Giuliano Reservoir	16657206	
Terre d'Apulia	Locone Reservoir	3842750	12390775
	Ofanto River	7875571	
	Wells	672454	
Ugento Li Foggi	Wells	1289079	1289079

The AQP network scheme reported in Figure 3 represents the basis for the strategic model of the system that is necessary to perform the numerical experiments. The topology of the model is illustrated in Figure 4, and its components are:

- Water reservoirs
- Water sources that can be distinguished in hydrological basins drained by the reservoirs, natural springs and wells
- Diversion mechanisms that distribute the water flow to the different users
- Agricultural districts
- Industrial districts
- Drinking water network

Figure 4: Topologic scheme of the strategic simulation model of the Apulia water system.

As shown in Figure 4, the system can be split into two subsystems. The first is the water storage system, managed by the districts (Consorti in the Italian terminology) that operate the reservoirs and supply water to the agricultural and industrial users. The second is the water distribution system, managed by AQPspa, that has to provide the potable water flows to the municipalities.

2.2 Baseline Scenario

The baseline scenario is a snapshot of the most recent stationary hydroclimatic and socio-economic conditions. It is based on the historical data of the last few decades. The hydrometeorological scenarios include the historical time series of hydrometeorological and water management variables (AQP supply/distribution and storage).

For the hydrometeorological variables, both reanalysis and observational time series have been considered (see Section 2.2.1). From the AQPspa management point of view, data from the abduction and distribution network are considered (see Section 2.2.2). Furthermore, it is fundamental to collect real data from each reservoir regulator. So far, only the water regulators of Occhito and Locone provided information sufficiently in advance for their analysis to adequately prepare the inputs, as outlined in Section 2.2.3. To make up for the lack of data, the Efas LISFLOOD dataset is considered and presented in Section 2.2.4. The baseline scenario contains finally the water demand for different uses, defined in Section 2.2.5.

A schematic review of the data available is reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Hydrometeorological and infrastructure data available.

Data	Quality	Time-Step	Type	Length	Source	Notes
Precipitation	Fair	Daily	Reanalysis	1951-Today	ECA&D (E-OBS)	Distributed dataset
Temperature	Fair	Daily	Reanalysis	1951-Today	ECA&D (E-OBS)	Distributed dataset
River discharge	Poor	Daily	Reanalysis	2009-2020	EFAS LISFLOOD	Distributed dataset
Reservoirs' volume	Fair	Daily	Measured	2000-2020	AQP	No Conza reservoir until 2016
Drinking water withdrawal	Fair	Daily	Measured	2006-2020	AQP	No Conza reservoir until 2017
Occhito Level	Good	Daily	Measured	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	-
Occhito Volume	Good	Daily	Estimated	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	-
Occhito spillways release	Good	Daily	Estimated	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	-
Finocchito Derivation (agricultural & drinking water)	Poor	Daily	-	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	Data frequency different from year to year
Occhito Inflows	Poor	Daily	Estimated	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	-
Occhito Precipitation	Fair	Daily	Measured	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	Missing data and negative values included
Occhito Temperature	Fair	Daily	Measured	2011-2021	C. Capitanata	-
Occhito (agricultural release)	Fair	Monthly	Measured	1983-2020	C. Capitanata	-
Occhito (drinking water release)	Fair	Monthly	Measured	1983-2020	C. Capitanata	-
Locone level	Good	Daily	Measured	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	-
Locone volume	Fair	Daily	Estimated	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	One month manually corrected (sep-2020)
Locone spillways outflow	Good	Daily	Estimated	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	-
Locone (agricultural release)	Good	Daily	Measured	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	-
Locone (drinking water release)	Poor	Daily	Measured	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	Not always matching AQP withdrawal declaration
Locone inflow	Poor	Daily	Estimated	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	-
Locone Pumping to Minervino Alto	Poor	Daily	Measured	2010-2020	C. Terre d'Apulia	Some internal incoherence
Locone temperature	Fair	10-days	Measured	2016-2021	C. Terre d'Apulia	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Locone precipitation	Fair	10-days	Measured	2016-2021	C. Terre d'Apulia	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Pertusillo precipitation	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Pertusillo temperature	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Pertusillo level	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Pertusillo volume	Fair	Daily	Estimated	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Pertusillo inflow	Fair	Daily	Estimated	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed

Pertusillo (agricultural release)	Poor	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza level	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza volume	Fair	Daily	Estimated	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza spillways release	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza (agricultural release)	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza (drinking release)	Fair	Daily	Measured	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed
Conza inflows	Fair	Daily	Estimated	2010-2021	EIPLI	Internal incoherence, further analysis needed

2.2.1 Precipitation and Temperature

To better understand the system, precipitation and temperature trends are here considered.

Temperature trends have been progressively increasing, and rates of change have become noticeably more intense during the last 25 years. Recently, the Apulia Region has been alternatively affected by extreme events related to anomalous climatic years, i.e., droughts in 2011–2012, floods in 2013–2014, and rapid fluctuations of droughts/floods in 2008–2009 (Ronco et al., 2017). Lionello et al. (2014) studied precipitation and temperature time series in Apulia. They highlighted trends toward warmer and marginally drier conditions during the whole analysed (1951-2005) period: +0.18°C/decade in mean annual minimum temperature and -14.9mm/decade in the total annual precipitation. Precipitation and temperature data are obtained from the European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECA&D) database. Maximum, minimum, and daily average temperatures are presented in a daily gridded dataset with a spatial resolution of 0.1 x 0.1 degrees (lat, long) in a regular grid over the European continent. The gridded database is obtained by ECA&D by interpolation of the gauge stations and undergoes quality control to remove outliers and make sure the stations adopt homogeneous standards on data retrieval. Precipitation and

Figure 5: Apulia Region: precipitation and temperature ensemble (shades of grey) and cyclostationary mean (red)

temperature are the main drivers of droughts, therefore, a first look at their time evolution allows to gain some preliminary insights on the trends on the time horizon of this analysis. Figure 5 shows the cyclostationary mean of precipitation intensity (mm) and temperature (°C) for the Apulia Region.

In Figure 6, the precipitation and temperature cyclostationary mean evaluated at Occhito reservoir are reported. In this case, a much more jagged trend is observed, especially for the precipitation, which also has a slightly lower excursion. On the other hand, the temperature instead has an almost identical minimum value but a wider range. However, we remind you that this compares data obtained from a reanalysis dataset and data measured on the ground through sensors near the Occhito dam.

Figure 6: Occhito reservoir: precipitation and temperature ensemble (shades of grey) and cyclostationary mean (red)

2.2.2 AQP data

Historical data of the water circulating in the system is needed to calibrate and validate models and create a comparative baseline.

At first, an exploration of Institutional sitography has been carried out in order to understand the availability of public institutional data. ARPA, Distretto Appennino Meridionale, EIPLI, Acquedotto Pugliese, Regione Puglia, Protezione Civile Puglia and Irrigation Districts websites were consulted.

We obtained temperature and precipitation time series from this exploratory phase, together with reservoirs' volume data (AQP data).

The storage data of the main four reservoirs (Occhito, Monte Cotugno, Pertusillo and Locone) are here considered. Unfortunately, the Conza time series were not long enough to be included in this part of the analysis.

Figure 7: Storage level cyclostationary mean.

Figure 8: Reservoirs' behaviour over time.

From AQP bulletins, reservoirs' storage and drinking water release are acquired.

As expected, storage recharge begins in winter and continues until spring; then precipitation becomes lower, temperatures and water demand rise, so reservoirs' levels are lowered in late spring/summer to satisfy the water demand (see Figure 7). Furthermore, it is interesting to note how the trend over the period of interest emphasises the critical years for the system (see Figure 8). This is even clearer in Figure 9, where the total amount of water is considered, and an overview of the system capacity and behaviour over time is provided. Since the reservoir levels reached very low values, it can be inferred that 2001-2002, 2007-2008, and 2017 were dry years.

Figure 9: Sum of reservoirs' storage behaviour over time.

2.2.3 Data from the Irrigation Districts

Local authorities have been contacted, and the main variables of Occhito and Locone Reservoirs were obtained from Capitanata and Terre d'Apulia Districts for the time horizon 2010-2020:

- Reservoirs' level and storage
- Precipitation and temperature measured at the dams
- Agricultural water release
- Drinking water release
- Outflow (spillways)

Figure 10: Locone total outflows.

Figure 11: Occhito total outflows.

Figure 11 shows that the behaviour of the outflows for the two reservoirs is quite different. In particular, Occhito experienced spillways outflows, and Locone didn't. As confirmed by the Locone's operator, this is due to the regulation boundaries kept far below the dam maximum regulation height. Furthermore, Occhito keeps daily records of agricultural and drinking water aggregated and relatively constant during the month, while Locone separates those releases and records them daily.

Some of these data are missing, incoherent, or simply mistaken, but they represent a starting point for the creation of a baseline for the model.

2.2.4 EFAS LISFLOOD data

Due to the poor amount, quality, and length of some of the data obtained, we considered using a reanalysis dataset from EFAS, LISFLOOD.

The European Flood Awareness System (EFAS), jointly developed by the European Commission and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts ([ECMWF](http://www.ecmwf.int/)³), is a hydrological forecast and monitoring system independent of administrative and political boundaries in the greater European domain. The aim of EFAS is to support preparatory measures before major flood events strike, particularly in the large trans-national river basins and throughout Europe in general. EFAS is the first operational European system monitoring and forecasting floods across Europe and is a component of the [Copernicus Emergency Management Service](https://www.copernicus.eu/en/services/emergency)⁴.

The hydrological model used for EFAS is LISFLOOD⁵. The model represents a hybrid between a conceptual and a physical rainfall-runoff model combined with a routing module in the river channel. LISFLOOD has been specifically designed for large river catchments (de Roo, 1999; van der Knijff and de Roo, 2006).

The data presented in the previous section, various in length and quality, made it possible to calculate the net inflows to the reservoirs by closing the water budget. A first reconnaissance study related to the potential advantage of using this type of data has been undertaken. A comparison of inflows generated closing the daily balance for the Occhito and Locone reservoirs with the LISFLOOD outputs is shown in Figure 12.

³ <http://www.ecmwf.int/>

⁴ <https://www.copernicus.eu/en/services/emergency>

⁵ <https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood/>

Reanalysis data show an apparent discrepancy from the data provided by Irrigation Districts both in terms of timing and magnitude. Therefore, the LISFLOOD data are considered unreliable (probably) due to the reduced extension of the system under exam and are, therefore, unusable for reservoirs for which no measured series is yet available.

Figure 12: Comparison of LISFLOOD and the net inflow of Locone (on the left) and Occhito (on the right) reservoirs (elaboration of data obtained from Consortia).

2.2.5 Water Demand

In order to compute the objective related to the water supply deficit (see Section 3.1.2), constituting part of the socio-economic component of the baseline scenario, water demands need to be estimated for each Irrigation District.

Regione Puglia and the *Autorità di Bacino della Puglia* (the regional water authority) realised a study (ABRP2) where hydrological needs for the cultivated areas have been evaluated through a distributed model (1km x 1km cells), considering soil use, groundwater levels, plant's needs, rain, and temperature. Results of this modelling exercise have been aggregated at the monthly time step for each Consortium, as reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Estimated agricultural water requirements.

Irr. District	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year
Arneo	115961	333696	263135	601209	1434630	2966779	3720491	3497956	1565182	412975	209559	92009	15213582
Capitanata	4880044	9397565	15038165	18431924	20715272	20663187	29962812	29411366	12033390	15572613	6651994	4132996	186891328
Gargano	20781	42204	79149	91719	123773	137506	171198	177600	58027	91411	26155	9789	1029312
Terre d'Apulia	126022	271025	310759	794222	1743943	3620504	5256904	5080122	2396438	608515	171909	113728	20494091
Stornara e Tara	568189	1147473	1039899	2690431	5038578	9646376	12338350	12285794	6339069	1741887	917409	430393	54183848
Ugento Li Foggi	72855	216666	193907	41292	670496	1152927	1502505	1341271	502101	225516	126107	51956	6097599

These numbers have been compared with the average amount of water historically distributed by each irrigation district and reported in Table 4, where also water sources used by each district are reported.

Table 4: Estimated water need and actual distribution.

Irrigation District	Mean of cubic meters distributed/year	Estimated Water Needs/year	% distributed/needed	Source
Arneo	498373	15213582	3.3	100% wells
Capitanata	100051741	186891328	53.5	63% Occhito Reservoir, 11% Ofanto River, and 26% Marana Capacciotti Reservoir
Gargano	186566	1029312	18.1	95% springs, 5% wells
Terre d'Apulia	11027954	20494091	53.8	35% Locone reservoir, 65% Ofanto River
Stornara e Tara	39755333	54183848	73.4	58% Monte Cotugno Reservoir, 42% San Giuliano Reservoir
Ugento Li Foggi	1289079	6097599	21.1	100% wells

The volumes of water supplied by the consortia are consistently smaller than the water demand. In fact, according to Sardaro et al., 2018, distributed water is less than a quarter of water demand, and farmers tend to overexploit groundwater.

To assess the amount of water that needs to be released by each reservoir into the system to satisfy the water demand, the historical mean fraction among sources that provides water to each Irrigation District has been considered. This fraction has been applied to obtain a monthly pattern of the amount of water supplied, as shown in Table 5.

For example, Occhito provides 63% of the water supplied by the Capitanata Irrigation District. Consequently, Occhito should satisfy 63% of the estimated agricultural water needs of the same Irrigation District.

This method has been used to design the agricultural water demand for Locone and Occhito Reservoirs.

The reservoirs of Monte Cotugno, Pertusillo and Conza supply water (also) to some irrigation districts outside Puglia. Therefore, we do not have the same contextual information to undertake the same type of comparison. Accordingly, to estimate the irrigation water demand, historical data provided by the reservoir regulators was used to design an equivalent model for each reservoir. The suggested water demands are reported in Table 5 and Figure 13.

Table 5: Estimated mean monthly water demand [m3/s].

Reservoirs	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Locone	0	0	0	0	0.0436	0.3885	0.7094	0.6958	0.3858	0.0933	0.0042	0
Occhito	0.2427	0.2819	0.4932	1.7149	4.1704	8.9371	12.5698	7.7236	2.9969	1.7608	1.0502	0.4264
Monte Cotugno	0.4948	0.4716	0.9763	2.1333	7.5684	10.5365	11.9826	11.6384	8.6181	5.1944	1.4757	0.5990
Pertusillo	0	0	0	0	1.5750	3.082	6.785	5.838	1.800	1.134	0	0
Conza	0.0900	0.3223	0.5000	0.5000	1.6500	4.6467	5.0667	5.6467	3.2415	0.9538	0.4920	0.2107

Figure 13: The water irrigation demand related to each reservoir considered.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 compare the estimated water demand and the actual water released by the Irrigation Districts.

Figure 14: Comparison of estimated water demand and actual release from Locone to Minervino Alto sub-district (Terre d'Apulia).

A bigger-than-estimated water demand release could be due to water loss through the distribution network.

Figure 15: Comparison of estimated water demand and actual release from Occhito to Fortore sub-district (Capitanata).

2.3 Drought characterisation and analysis

Repeated sequences of drought years affect all water supply systems, causing consequences both on the satisfaction of the drinking requirement, which is a priority, and on the agricultural sector. Drought is, in fact, one of the main causes of desertification, i.e., the decrease or disappearance of the productivity of the land. However, a unanimous and precise definition of drought is still missing. For a review of the main definitions, the analysis of the potential impacts and the evolution of this phenomenon, see the Appendix.

Italy is increasingly affected by droughts, particularly in the southern regions. The droughts that occurred in the early 2000s, particularly in 2003, caused serious consequences, with severe curtailing and large crop losses, also attracting the attention of the news press at the national level.

Tools for detecting and characterising droughts are key to supporting the evaluation of water portfolios both with respect to the baseline and the scenarios obtained from climate projections. An extensive review of the main drought indicators and their characteristics is given in the Appendix. Here, we report the results of the analysis carried out for the Apulia region for the years 1951-2018.

2.3.1 Drought analysis

A drought analysis has been performed with the computation of some common drought indicators among the ones proposed by ISPRA in its Guidelines ISPRA (2018). All the chosen indicators belong to the SPI family for their characteristics of scalability, comparability, and immediacy discussed in the previous sections. The computed indicators are the following:

- Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI)
- Standardised Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)
- Standardised Runoff Index (SRI)

All the indicators have been evaluated at a weekly time step for multiple time aggregations: 1 month, 3 months, 6 months and 1 year. These time aggregations were chosen to capture all drought types. Short time aggregations capture quick variability in water resources and monitor meteorological droughts, medium time aggregation monitor agricultural droughts, and long aggregations monitor hydrological droughts.

The longest time-series available of SPI, SPEI and SRI are shown in Figure 16, Figure 17 and Figure 18 respectively. The SPI and SPEI indicators show an increasing frequency of extreme events in recent years; this trend is not detected with SRI.

Figure 16: SPI time series in Apulia Region from 1951 to 2018.

Figure 17: SPEI time series in Apulia Region from 1951 to 2018.

Figure 18: SRI time series in Apulia Region from 1980 to 2018.

In Figure 19, the different boxes represent different time aggregations of the three indicators. 1-month aggregation SRI seems to be more able in detecting droughts than 1-month SPI and 1-month SPEI. SPI's accuracy increases by enlarging the time aggregation, while SPEI's doesn't.

(a) 1-month

(b) 3-months

(c) 6-months

(d) 12-months

Figure 19: Different time aggregation for SPI family indicators.

The computed indicators allow a preliminary detection of past drought events in the basin. In addition, using the indicators of the SPI family, the onset and the ending of a drought can be assessed. Conventionally, a drought is set to start when the indicator falls below -1 for two consecutive months and ends when it turns positive. Figure 20 reports the result of the drought detection analysis. The solid lines represent the drought periods identified by each indicator following the colour code on the left. Despite a non-homogeneous behaviour, most indicators indicate time spans around 2001-2002, 2007-2008 and 2017-2018 as dry periods (consistently with what was declared by the stakeholders and local press), with different indexes pointing at different months as the most critical. SPI12 and SPEI12 point out a continuous dry period in 2001-2002, while the others report it as intermittent drought periods. Overall, SRI seems to be the most consistent indicator. Notably, SRI and SPEI spot a drought straddling 2011 and 2012 while SPI does not. In conclusion, indicators show similarities in the identified drought periods, although differences are also relevant as far as the dry period's onset, persistence, and termination are concerned.

Figure 20: Indicator's detection according to their definition.

The same analyses have been performed at the Irrigation District level, and similar results have been obtained.

2.4 Aquator

Under the supervision of the University of Palermo, AQPspa built a complete model of its distribution network a few years ago, using a well-known commercial software, Aquator.

2.4.1 The software

Aquator is a software application produced by Oxford Scientific to simulate complex water resource systems with a daily time-step. The real system is represented by a schematic graph model built using a 'drag & drop' user interface, selecting appropriate components from the Aquator Toolbox.

Examples of components are river and groundwater abstractions, uni- and bi-directional links (to connect other components), blenders (to mix incoming water in a specified ratio or to maintain a specified level of water quality), bulk supplies (for example, to force usage of the entire maximum amount that is available), catchments (to define a simple flow series of daily or monthly average values), demand centres, discharges, diversions, gauging stations, hydro-generators, pumping stations, regulators and reservoirs, terminations, water treatment plants. Components could be eventually grouped to encapsulate uniform rules for the contained elements. Each component or group could be associated with a license to limit the amount of water supplied over a defined

Figure 21: An example of a simple model defined in Aquator (from the Aquator Manual).

period. An example of a simple model considering different types of components and links is reported in Figure 21. Once the components have been linked together and all specific hydrological parameters assigned, the model may be run over any pre-defined horizon. At the end of the simulation, it is possible (see Figure 22) to produce a complete report of the behaviour of all the components and the selected variables may be displayed in graphical and tabular form.

The main features of Aquator are the following:

- Component-based. Models are constructed by joining together components representing hydrological entities, using an intuitive point-and-click user interface. These components encapsulate the operating rules that govern their use. For example, a reservoir component will typically have control curves that the reservoir operating rules will use to determine releases from the reservoir.
- Customisable and extensible. It incorporates Microsoft® Visual Basic® for Applications (VBA), the same technology used in the Microsoft Office suite of applications. With this tool, the user can optionally customise the operating rules of any component. In the same way, third-party developers could add additional components.
- Standards and Open architecture based. The design and implementation of Aquator components and Aquator itself are based on an industry-standard open architecture called COM (Component Object Model) defined by Microsoft and used as the VBA architecture.
- Cooperative. The Aquator application itself can be used as a type of component. For example, a GIS (Geographic Information System) application could automatically load Aquator and create a model from the information held in the GIS database.
- Globally-optimized. The facility “Aqua Solver” looks for the ‘best’ solution for water allocation to meet demand.

Each model and parameters configuration are organised as a different project, stored in a single database. The current version of Aquator uses an SQLite database file (AXVDBS extension). An Aquator database can contain any number of projects (models), time series and profile data, and results from model runs.

Input time-series, as, for example, the water demand of each demand centre, could be imported in Aquator, with the “copy & paste” feature from clipboard data or with the excel import wizard. Simulation results could be exported as plain text files (in “csv” format) or in excel format.

During each simulation day, water is moved according to the input data, the rules associated with each component, and the connectivity (the network) defined in the model.

Figure 22: The Aquator's form to visualize simulation results summary.

There are five phases to such water movements:

1. Any catchments in the model add to river flows at the start of the day. Such flows may be controlled by a simple time series of values or possibly by a full catchment model running at the same time.
2. The system's river regulators may augment river flows to satisfy river flow constraints and today's expected abstractions. If the forecasting option is turned on, then releases may also be made to satisfy flow constraints and predicted abstractions on future days.
3. Demand centres then try to satisfy their demands by drawing water from any or all available supplies, such as river abstractions, groundwater abstractions, reservoirs, etc. Demand is typically specified by a profile of daily demand values repeated each year but can be defined in other ways.
4. Reservoirs refill as necessary from their available supplies according to built-in rules governing refilling.
5. At the end of the day, any reservoir which has had excess water pushed into it will spill into its attached river spillway, possibly leading to further spills from any other downstream connected reservoirs.

These movements of water could be limited considering different physical and legal constraints, eventually specifying the order in which operators, if any, release water. Also, the order in which the demand calculations are advanced could be defined automatically or manually, assuming different importance for different demand centres. Each day all the calculations following a defined advance order of components are completed before the calculations for the next advance order are started.

The optimisation algorithm could minimise both water deficits and costs, eventually considering together in a weighted combination.

2.4.2 The Apulian implementation

AQPspa operates all the services of storage, adduction, purification, and distribution of water for civil use, sewerage, and wastewater purification, including refinement for agricultural reuse.

The water supply system managed by AQPspa consists of several interconnected aqueduct networks with a transport potential of over 790 million cubic meters of water every year. Every day AQPspa enters its own aqueduct system on average 1.5 Mm³. It ensures the drinking water supply of over 4.5 million inhabitants distributed in Puglia, Basilicata, and Campania.

The water sources consist of natural springs for 29%, from artificial reservoirs for over 50%, and finally from over 200 wells. All fall within the Southern Apennine District and, overall, constitute a sufficient but not homogeneously distributed water availability and therefore require significant transfers between different Regions: from Molise to Campania and Puglia, from Lazio to Campania, from Campania to Puglia and Basilicata, and from Basilicata to Puglia and Calabria. The construction of the model required the definition of the monthly requests from the demand centres, assumed equal to the values delivered by AQPspa in 2012. An annual series of average monthly inflows was adopted for each reservoir, calculated based on historical values. Over 500 arches were modelled to connect over 250 nodes, including 4 hydroelectric plants, 6 lifting plants and 6 purification plants, 5 large reservoirs, 2 natural springs and over 30 groups of wells. A partial representation of the whole model is in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Sketch of a portion of the drinking water distribution scheme implemented in Aquator to give an idea of the complexity of the network.

The software carries out a global daily optimisation of the allocation of resources in terms of minimum cost and maximum satisfaction of requests, considering at the same time the losses in the sections of the channel and the plants as well as the maximum flow capacities.

The model represents the current hydraulic scheme and the existent pumping and hydropower systems and purification plants of the available sources⁶. It also allows you to simulate hypothetical water scarcity scenarios and

⁶ This model has been fine-tuned and refined over the years, up to a result deemed satisfactory and stable 4-5 years ago. Recently the company that produces the Aquator software, Oxford Scientific Software Ltd (<http://www.oxscisoft.com/>), has produced a completely new version (the XV) abandoned to keep the one used by AQPspa (the 4.3). The profound changes both in the data structure and in the characteristics of some components, as well as in the internal optimisation engines, currently prevent us from obtaining the previous results. Since last year, a recalibration of the model and an adaptation to the software's

possible structural interventions. For example, the simulation of a sudden rupture of the aqueduct fed by the Sinni reservoir (one of the main water carriers of the system) was achieved, with the consequent zeroing of the water supply that it normally guarantees.

new features has been underway, which AQPspa expects to complete in the next 2-to 3 months. The simulations that are the basis of the results in this deliverable will then be re-proposed on the final model, and eventually, the necessary corrections will be made.

3 Decision Analytic Framework

3.1 Water Portfolios

The twofold goals of T4.1 are to understand the trade-offs of the system and discover planning and management strategies that will withstand plausible, challenging conditions in the region (e.g., prolonged droughts, increasing demand, and contingencies in the system). Both goals require extensive exploration to understand the impacts of different hydroclimatic and socio-economic scenarios on the system's ability to meet its multi-sectorial demands. We build the relationship between the system's inputs and the relevant performance indicators described in the following. The idea is that the response model preserves the input and output behaviour of the original simulation-based model while removing the need to run a process-based model that will allow us to understand which candidate alternatives yield the best benefit for the system. For the Apulian system, a number of candidate water portfolios were identified, these are related to the management of existing infrastructure, such as reservoir control, increasing infrastructure capacity, such as doubling pipeline capacity and their connections within the system, re-activating non-conventional sources such as wells that are not currently considered into the system, as well as the integration of reuse technologies in feasible small water loops, described in more detail in the next Chapter and summarised here.

This baseline deliverable considers only the management of existing infrastructure, without any structural changes in the network, neither different water demands, water prices, treatments costs and unconventional sources connected, referring to the next deliverable, the complete exploration of the water portfolios.

3.1.1 Reservoir operations

Coordinated reservoir operations can play a key role in the system's reliability. For our initial abstraction of the Apulian Aqueduct system, we focus on four reservoirs that are relevant for the analysis of our performance indicators since they directly feed the system, and along with other sources such as Calore and Sele, along with other lateral flows not quantified in our analysis, contribute to the available water in the system. These reservoirs are mainly parallel to each other, that is, there is no cascading effect, hence the mass-balance dynamics can be computed separately.

3.1.2 Water diverted to farmers

Concerning the diversions to farmers, we consider the irrigation water demands defined in Par. 2.2.5. These are monthly values referring to each reservoir considered.

In the model, the water diverted to each district is defined as the minimum between the total water volume available, the allocation decision and the demand.

3.1.3 Water loops in the water supply system

The percent of water reuse refers to the volume of water that can be extended through water reuse technologies for the identified water loops. This alternative depends upon several specifications about the foreseen technology such as its scalability, that is, the volume that can be treated and integrated into the system, the costs for installation, operation, and maintenance, as well as the time when the technology can be scaled and incorporated into the system. This candidate alternative will enable us to understand the trade-off between the treatment cost, the benefit and the reliability gains of the overall system, and the technology's value when alleviating water supply during emergencies, especially during prolonged droughts, as discussed in the previous Section 2.3. It is also noteworthy that this alternative would be tested for feasible irrigation diversions and not for drinking water supply where there are more stringent regulations for water reuse for urban supply. Furthermore, the water diverted to farmers will consider alternative rates of water reuse corresponding to increasing investments and available technologies. This will potentially be reflected in water savings via water reuse will be ex-post associated with different technological solutions and narrative of future technological development and upscaling potential and associated costs.

3.1.4 Water loops in the water distribution systems

These alternatives will also be supplemented with a few structural decisions, which are currently under consideration by the AQPspa, for instance, expanding the canal capacity in certain parts of the system and integrating alternative water sources, such as impounded sources which are not currently part of the network that could be reactivated and could increase the reliability of the system. This includes the reactivation of several wells, which provide a good opportunity to explore treatment technologies.

3.1.5 Infrastructure alternatives

Infrastructural planning alternatives currently under consideration are strengthening the Occhito dam connection, doubling the pipe capacity in the Sinni scheme, and a new pumping plant in Parco del Marchese potabilisation plant.

3.2 Indicators

Project \hat{O} follows the Participatory and Integrated Planning procedure by Soncini-Sessa et al. (2007) to infer and represent decision-makers (DM) and stakeholders (SH) preferences. First, stakeholders with similar issues and priorities are grouped into sectors (e.g., irrigation supply, drinking water). Then, for each sector, an evaluation criterion is specified and associated with an index that DMs and/or SHs can use for the comparative assessment of the portfolios with respect to the criterion. The index can be defined either on an ordinal scale (qualitative) or on a cardinal scale (quantitative). It must be a function of the portfolio that describes the preferred direction of change embedded in the evaluation criterion.

The index supports the pairwise comparison of alternative water portfolios. For example, given two portfolios P1 and P2, a DM should be able to select the “preferred portfolio” with respect to a given criterion by contrasting the values that the index assumes under P1 and P2. The repetition of such pairwise comparison across a set of portfolios allows the definition of the complete ranking of the portfolios with respect to the criterion expressed by the index. In principle, the index value can be directly estimated by interviewing the SHs or a representative expert when this is not feasible (Figure 24a). Yet, this direct approach frequently leads to subjective and hardly acceptable evaluations, and its implementation might become extremely difficult when the planning process involves many alternative portfolios. Therefore, an automated procedure is more appropriate to reproduce the SHs/Expert evaluations to compute the index (Figure 24b). The strong participation of both DMs and SHs is crucial in this step to ensure the results of the decision-making process will be perceived as trustable: direct involvement of the decision-maker herself in the modelling process is the unique way to make credible models: these can be built only by people who are familiar with both the problem and the institutional setting in which the problem is to be addressed (Loucks et al., 1985).

In Project \hat{O} , each index value can be computed as a function of the simulated trajectories of the relevant model variables (Figure 24c), such as water level in a specific river section, water flow in an irrigation canal, water flow through turbines in a hydropower plant. Such computation of the index is generally performed in two steps (Figure 24d). First, an evaluation indicator measures the effects of a portfolio in physical units. Then the value of this indicator is mapped into the actual satisfaction of the DMs’ or SH’ criterion by means of a value function.

It is worth noticing that the value of an indicator expressed in physical units could differ from the level of satisfaction of the associated criterion returned by the value function. For example, if the indicator quantifies the water level

Figure 24: Alternative approaches for the definition of evaluation index (adapted from Soncini-Sessa et al., 2007a).

excess above a critical flood threshold and portfolios P1, P2, and P3 produce different values of this indicator all above the threshold, the corresponding level of satisfaction can be null for all the three portfolios.

In some cases, it might be difficult to formulate an indicator directly associated with the index used by DMs or SHs for the evaluation of their criteria. For example, an indicator related to flood protection could be flood damage, which requires formalising a relationship between the water level in a flood event and the economic damages produced by the flood. However, defining such a relationship is very site-specific and generally requires ad-hoc data collections that may prevent its use in practice. In these cases, the original flood damage indicator might be replaced by a proxy indicator measuring the flooded area rather than the economic damage (Figure 24e). The proxy indicator is a variable in a logical relationship with the evaluation criterion associated with the index and related to the effects of the portfolios through a functional, objective, and potentially quantifiable link (Keeney and Raiffa, 1976). Then, DM/SHs can define a value function for the proxy indicator to map this latter into a level of satisfaction. The proxy indicator hence assumes the role of an indirect ordinal estimator of the evaluation criterion, and the degree of satisfaction of such criterion can be quantified through the value assumed by the proxy indicator, ultimately replacing the need for computing the original indicator.

In the Apulian site, the assessment indicators identified will aid the evaluation of planning and management policies for water distribution networks when incorporating alternative sources and water-reuse technologies within the system. We identify sustainable and efficient water management goals that respond to regional water needs while minimising the total costs of the distribution network and the technology costs. All the objectives will be optimised at a daily time scale for a planning horizon of $365T$, where T is the number of years considered in the planning time frame.

The main criteria can be categorised as follows:

1. Minimise water reuse costs. This objective is divided into two measurements, first, a water reduction cost related to the adoption of technologies for water reuse which is dependent upon the volume of water that will be treated by the reuse technology and is proportional to the percent water reduction in the system and the cost of the treatment technology at each point in time. The second evaluates the costs reduced by substituting pumping for irrigation where small water loops are implemented in the vicinity of the irrigation district.
2. Minimise costs in the water distribution network. The Apulian Aqueduct Authority currently optimises the distribution cost, and we also account for our objective formulation. The total cost of the water distribution network can be described as the sum of the operational costs, pumping costs, treatment costs, and rehabilitation or maintenance costs. Distribution points differentiate these costs.
3. Minimise water supply deficits. These objectives are considered for the following water demand sectors: 1) drinking supply; 2) farmers; 3) industry. A priority for suitable management policies is to provide a reliable source of drinking water to nearly 4.5 million users that depend upon the Apulian Aqueduct; other competing demands in the region are for farmers and for industrial use. This indicator aims to minimise the water supply deficit for each one of these users by minimising the squared difference between demand and the actual releases in cubic meters, where larger deficits are penalised more than smaller deficits.

Due to the narrow knowledge of some parts of the system and the limited availability of the dataset provided by other partners of the project, not all the indicators presented above can be computed in a reasonable way in each position of the system. We thus limit our optimisation procedure to a subset of indicators that, however, guarantees to be compliant with the scope of Project \hat{O} .

3.3 Scenarios

The simulation of the system requires the definition of a scenario, i.e., a set of input variables that we cannot control in the context of our optimal management problem but influence the dynamics of the system. Typical examples of these variables are the inflows, the water demands and the treatment costs.

In this project, the scenario is defined as the set $\omega = \{q_1^h; wirr_0^{h-1}; wind_0^{h-1}; wdri_0^{h-1}; cdri_0^{h-1}\}$, where q_1^h is the vector of all inflows, $wirr_0^{h-1}; wind_0^{h-1}; wdri_0^{h-1}$ are the specific water demands, and $cdri_0^{h-1}$ represents the vector of all adduction, treatment, and distribution costs depending on the structural configuration and used technologies.

In the deliverable D4.1, we focus on the baseline scenario ($\bar{\omega}$), constituted by observed historical inflows and structural factors.

Our framework is not limited to historical conditions but allows us to consider the management optimisation over a future scenario ($\hat{\omega}$), which will be the object of the deliverable D4.4. The future scenarios analysis allows us to consider potential changes in the hydrologic, structural, and economic conditions. These changes in the external drivers will lead to new management strategies specifically designed to be efficient for the future system's conditions.

3.4 Water portfolios design

As said, the DAF requires defining the water system operation as an optimisation problem to derive an efficient management strategy. To this aim, the indicators (all of them or just a subset) presented in the previous section can be used as the objectives to be minimised (if costs) or maximised (if benefits). Following a multi-objective approach, we can consider a generic K -dimensional vector of operating objectives $J = [J^1, \dots, J^K]$ for the DAF optimisation.

Each single objective function is formulated as follows:

$$J_{\omega}^k = \Psi_{q_1, \dots, q_h} \left[\Phi_{0, \dots, h} \left(g_1^k(s_0, u_0, q_1), \dots, g_h^k(s_h) \right) \right] \quad k = 1, \dots, K \quad (1)$$

where

- s_t is the state of the system at time t ,
- u_t is the control decision taken to manage the system operation,
- q_{t+1} is the stochastic disturbance,
- ω is the scenario,
- h is the length of the time horizon,
- $g_t^k(\cdot)$ is the step cost (or benefit) relative to the k^{th} objective,
- $\Psi[\cdot]$ is a disturbance filtering criterion (e.g., expected value) for filtering the uncertainty introduced by the disturbance q_{t+1} ,
- $\Phi(\cdot)$ is an operator for time aggregation (e.g., mean or sum).

The core of the optimal control problem is the management policy that defines the control action as a function of the information available at time t , I_t :

$$u_t = p(I_t) \quad (2)$$

Most of the times, I_t corresponds to the state of the system s_t . However, it is possible to include in the information vector every variable known at time t , including forecasted values for the future steps or exogenous information that can be useful to estimate the future evolution of the system (see, for instance, the drought indexes discussed in Section 2.3). Given the objectives vector and the operating policy, the optimisation problem is simply defined as $\text{opt}_p J$.

The model's equations representing the optimisation problem constraints, the characterisation of the objectives and the algorithm adopted to solve the problem are described in the following sections.

4 Models and tools

In this section, we provide an in-depth description of the strategic model presented in Figure 4, which is reported for convenience in a. We then present the model's components and describe the elements and tools necessary for the system's simulation and optimisation.

4.1 Strategic model

The key components of the strategic simulation model adopted in this work are the five water reservoirs Occhito, Conza, Locone, Pertusillo and Monte Cotugno, each draining its catchment. Catchments are not modelled as we adopt a partial-data driven approach (see Section 2.2), which directly relies on observational data for the uncontrolled and control-independent components of the system. Streamflow data are derived as net inflow by inverting equation 3 and using historical time series of storages and releases (see Section 2.2 for an in-depth analysis of the inflows). Two other water sources are implemented in the strategic model: the natural springs of Cassano and Caposele and the Salento region wells system that extracts groundwater flows from the aquifer.

Downstream of each reservoir, a diversion dam distributes the release among different water users. With the only exception of Monte Cotugno reservoir, which is used to supply water to an industrial district, all the dams serve both an irrigation district and the drinking water distribution network.

We illustrate the mathematical model of the AQP topology considering a generic single-reservoir model connected through a river stretch with a diversion point (b) serving three different types of users (agricultural, industrial, and potable water). The environmentally vulnerable river stretches downstream of the reservoir are usually protected by the legislation by means of a constraint on the water release (the minimum environmental flow). Note that, each reservoir usually is also connected to a hydropower plant. However, since this aspect is not considered in this study, we did not report this element in the figure.

Figure 25: Topological scheme of the strategic simulation model (a) and illustrative example of a single-reservoir subsystem (b).

The reservoir dynamics are described by the water volume's mass balance equation s_t stored in the reservoir at the beginning of month t :

$$s_{t+1} = s_t + q_{t+1} - r_{t+1} \quad (3)$$

where q_{t+1} is the net inflow to the reservoir (i.e., inflow minus evaporation losses and other minor phenomena such as the seepage losses) in the time interval $[t; t + 1)$ and r_{t+1} the volume of water released in the same time interval. In the adopted notation, the time subscript of a variable indicates the instant when its value is

deterministically known. The storage s_t is observed at time t , whereas the inflow has subscript $t + 1$, denoting the realisation of the inflow stochastic process in the time interval $[t; t + 1)$.

The release is defined as $r_{t+1} = f(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1})$, where $f(\cdot)$ describes the non-linear, stochastic relation between the release decision determined by the operating policy, i.e., $u_t = p(\cdot)$, and the actual release r_{t+1} (Piccardi and Soncini-Sessa, 1991). The actual release at the end of the time interval is generally equal to the release decision unless physical constraints prohibit it (e.g., if the prescribed release lies outside the minimum and maximum allowable releases, if there is insufficient water to meet the prescribed release, or if the prescribed release would result in the reservoir storage capacity being exceeded).

The water released from the reservoir is distributed to the different users through a regulated diversion mechanism. The volume of water diverted to agricultural districts, industries and the aqueduct are $rirr_{t+1}$, $rind_{t+1}$ and $rdri_{t+1}$ and should ideally fulfil the corresponding water demands. Downstream the irrigation diversion, the water volume that is left in the river should guarantee adequate environmental conditions to preserve the ecosystem.

As said, the generic elements described above have to be individually calibrated and validated and then integrated to build the model of the entire Apulia water system (see a). For instance, each reservoir has its own characteristics (e.g. level-surface-storage relationship and specific functions that define its minimum and maximum releases) that have to be incorporated in the corresponding model component.

It is worth noting that the AQP component in Figure 4 represents the water distribution system implemented with the Aquator tool (see Section 2.4) and used to compute the AQP-related indicators (drinking water distribution deficit and cost). This is the only component of the strategic model that is not directly implemented in C++ but requires executing external software. Evaluating the water portfolios and identifying the Pareto efficient ones requires exploring millions (or thousands) of candidate solutions via simulation. Given its real-to-run ratio (a simulation on a one-year time horizon requires approximatively one hour of computing time), Aquator is not a suitable tool for our scope. To avoid these practical and computational issues, we use a surrogate model that will be presented in detail in Section 4.2.

4.1.1 Objectives

When considering complex water systems such as the Apulia one, several stakeholders with conflicting interests are usually affected by the reservoir's operations and the diversion. These conflicting interests are captured by the indicators introduced in Section 3.2, which are here converted into the objectives of the optimisation framework. Within the strategic model represented in Figure 4, three main stakeholders' sectors (i.e., agriculture, industry, and potable water distribution) may be affected by the system's operations. Their conflicting interests can be thus modelled as a four-objectives vector $J = [J^{irr}, J^{ind}, J^{dri,d}, J^{dri,c}]$, whose components are the following:

- Squared irrigation deficit:

$$J^{irr} = \frac{1}{h} [\sum_{t=0}^{h-1} (\max(wirr_t - rirr_{t+1}, 0))^2] \quad (4)$$

where $wirr_t$ and $rirr_{t+1}$ are the irrigation water demand and supply.

- Squared industrial deficit:

$$J^{ind} = \frac{1}{h} [\sum_{t=0}^{h-1} (\max(wind_t - rind_{t+1}, 0))^2] \quad (5)$$

where $wind_t$ and $rind_{t+1}$ are the industrial water demand and supply respectively.

- Potable water deficit, $J^{dri,d}$:

unlike the two objectives defined above, we cannot directly compute $J^{dri,d}$ as the deficit between the drinking water demand, $wdri_t$, and the corresponding supply, $rdri_{t+1}$. The reason is that there is not a direct correspondence between demand and supply: the water flows are released in the complex water distribution system implemented in Aquator.

- Drinking water distribution cost, $J^{dri,c}$:

As $J^{dri,d}$, also the distribution cost cannot be easily expressed with single mathematical formulation but requires a specific model (again, Aquator).

Note that the objectives are computed in different points of the system, i.e., in each agricultural and industrial district and in the specific points defined in Aquator. However, this would generate an unsustainable number of objectives. We thus decide to aggregate the objectives by summing the values obtained in the different points of the system. Intermediate solutions with partial aggregation of the objectives can be easily considered with our software. The four objectives considered are deficits or costs and thus are to be minimised.

4.1.2 Decision variables

The optimisation of the system management requires to operate the reservoir dams and the diversions. The reservoir dam operation problem requires sequential release decisions u_t to be taken at discrete time instants based on the current state of the system (t, s_t) (i.e., time, reservoir storage) or the pair time, current information (t, I_t) . The decision u_t is determined at each time step by a closed-loop operating policy $u_t = p(t, s_t)$. In order to solve the system management optimisation problem, this operating policy $p(\cdot)$ must be thus optimised with respect to multiple objectives. Note that, in our formulation of the problem, u_t also contains the fraction of water to be distributed between the different water users in the diversion nodes and the total amount of water captured by the well fields. This multi-objective optimisation problem must be solved for each possible portfolio, namely every combination of possible infrastructural interventions (i.e., different distribution network and irrigation expansion). For each portfolio, a set of Pareto-optimal solutions (i.e., operating policies) will be thus generated according to the trade-off among conflicting objectives (see previous section).

4.2 Surrogate model of Aquator

As reported in Section 2.4, the drinking water distribution system managed by AQP is currently implemented in the Aquator Toolbox. In principle, Aquator could be nested in the strategic model to compute the drinking water deficit and the AQP distribution costs, the two objectives that represent the performance of the aqueduct management. However, this would lead to huge computational costs (a computing time greater than 4000 days for a 10-year horizon and 10,000 function evaluation, a relatively small number for a many-objective problem as the one at hand), making the problem practically intractable due to the high number of simulations required to find reasonable results in the optimisation procedure.

A widely adopted method to solve this issue consists in building a surrogate model (sometimes named also response surface) to replace the original one (Aquator in this case) (Castelletti et al. 2010a, Castelletti et al. 2010b, Castelletti et al. 2011). The surrogate model is not required to describe the physical processes with the same level of detail of the original high-fidelity model it surrogates; its aim is to reproduce the relationship between a set of input variables (i.e., the water flows released into the aqueduct into the aqueduct) and a corresponding set of outputs (drinking water deficit and the distribution costs) in a straightforward and computationally efficient way. A schematic representation of the surrogate modelling framework is reported in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Surrogate modelling framework.

The implementation of a surrogate model usually follows a 3-step procedure:

1. Input/output samples generation via design of experiments (sampling of the input space) and simulation of the original high-fidelity model.
2. Selection of the surrogate structure and optimisation of its parameters.
3. Testing phase and evaluation of the accuracy of the surrogate.

In the first phase, we generate the input/output pairs (see Figure 26) running multiple parallel simulation of Aquator. These data constitute the dataset used in the surrogate model identification process. We sample the input space following two different kinds of experiments. The first consists of a grid search approach with an exhaustive evaluation of the rectangular grid. The specific values for each input are selected basing on a statistical analysis of the range of values covered by the historical data. Minimum and maximum water flows into the aqueduct are selected as extreme values. In addition, we consider two intermediate values (selected looking at the density functions of the data). Using this rectangular grid (all the possible combinations are considered), we are sure to cover the whole input hyperspace and to avoid using the surrogate model in extrapolation.

The second set of experiments makes use of the time series available. By means of a clustering procedure (performed by the mean-shift algorithm), we identify the pattern in the historical data and make use of the centroids that are representative of the process. Historical data are fundamental to improve the accuracy of the surrogate model in the areas of the hypervolume containing the combinations of inputs that are more likely to occur in the future, since they occurred in the past.

The second step requires to select a suitable architecture for the reduced model and to train it. Machine learning models are usually adopted to this aim for their flexibility and high performance in terms of accuracy and computing time. Here we adopt artificial neural networks with a feed-forward structure. As reported in Figure 27, the model receives as input the water flow discharged into the aqueduct (from the reservoirs, the natural springs and the wells) and the water demand pattern and computes the two AQP objectives: drinking water deficit and the associated distribution costs.

Figure 27: Neural architecture of the Aquator surrogate model.

The neural network is implemented in Python⁷ programming language using Keras⁸, a high-level open-source library that provides an interface for TensorFlow⁹. Keras provides built-in functions for building neural architectures and auto-differentiation algorithms for their training. Our implementation allows to consider an arbitrary number of hidden neurons and layers, and different activation functions. In addition, we compare a wide range of gradient-based algorithms for the model's training. According to the traditional guidelines in the field, input and output variables are rescaled into the range $[0; 1]$ to avoid numerical issues.

In term of coding, the main issue is that we identified the surrogate model in Python, while the main routine for simulation and optimisation is in C++. In principle, it is possible to call the Python model inside the C++ routine (for instance, making use of a wrapper), but this would unavoidably slow down the execution of the code. We thus

⁷ <https://www.python.org/>

⁸ <https://keras.io/>

⁹ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

decided to store the optimal parameters' values computed in Python in text files and load them into C++. The neural architecture is thus rebuilt in native C++ to delete any possible source of inefficiency in the program execution.

As it is common practice in the machine learning applications, we split the available dataset, generated by Aquator simulation, into train, validation and test set. As suggested by its name, the first is used to compute the gradients of the model's parameters (i.e., weights and biases) during the optimisation. The second is not directly involved in the gradient descend, but it is hold out to monitor the risk of overfitting and to set the value of the hyperparameters.

Figure 28: Loss function evolution during the training epochs (first 60 epochs shown for an 8-neuron architecture)

Figure 28 shows an example of the MSE evolution during the epochs of optimisation. The training loss function rapidly decreases in the first epochs and then keep evolving with a marginal improvement to a final value. MSE trends in training and validation are almost coincident, meaning that the model is not overfitting the training data.

We performed a grid search on the following hyperparameters:

- training algorithm (stochastic gradient descent and Adam optimiser);
- non-linear activation function (linear, sigmoid, rectified linear unit);
- batch size;
- learning rate;
- number of neurons in the hidden layer.

This latter is a crucial hyperparameter since it defines the surrogate model's architecture. As shown in Figure 29, we obtain high accuracy with a limited number of neurons. With 8 neurons, the R^2 is higher than 0.99, and this value does not improve significantly when adding more hidden units, meaning that it can be considered as an appropriate model complexity. Given the high performance obtained with a single-layer neural network, we do not test deep architectures (with more than one hidden layer). This relatively simple architecture allows limiting the computational cost, whose increment would turn out to be critical in the policy identification stage.

Figure 29: Surrogate model performance obtained with a different complexity (in terms of number of neurons in the hidden layer).

Once the neural surrogate model has been identified, the usual testing phase is performed to assess the model accuracy and to check the model’s appropriateness for our task (e.g., absence of under/overfitting on the training or validation datasets). Each panel of Figure 30 reports the output obtained simulating Aquator and the corresponding value (i.e., computed with the same inputs) estimated by the surrogate model.

Perfect estimations lie on the diagonal line (in blue in the figure), that is the set of all points for which the Aquator output is equal to the surrogate estimation. As it can be seen, in all the considered cases, the points are well aligned on the perfect-estimation line. This means that our surrogate model provides solutions with high accuracy and the absence of overfitting.

The numerical values of the R^2 scores of the surrogate model obtained on the train, validation and test set are reported in Table 6.

Table 6: Surrogate model accuracy in terms of R^2 , computed on train, validation and test set (8 hidden neurons).

Output variable	Train	Validation	Test
Drinking water deficit [m^3/s]	0.9950	0.9949	0.9947
AQP distribution cost [$k\text{€}/d$]	0.9877	0.9875	0.9874

The performance index reported in the table further confirms that the surrogate model is not overfitting the values obtained by the Aquator simulation. Conversely, the surrogate has high precision and generalisation capability. It

Figure 30: Comparison between Aquator output and corresponding surrogate values for training, validation and test set. The blue line represents the perfect estimation, i.e., corresponding Aquator and surrogate values.

can thus substitute the original aqueduct simulation model in the C++ routine.

4.3 Optimisation tool

The design problem of an optimal operating policy for water systems traditionally employs dynamic programming (DP) and its stochastic extension (SDP) (Yeh, 1985). SDP formulates the operating policy design problem as a sequential decision-making process, where a decision taken now produces an immediate reward, affects the next system state and, through that, all the subsequent rewards. The search for optimal policies employs value functions defined over a discrete (or discretised) state-decision space, which are obtained by looking ahead to future events

and computing a backed-up value.

The decision u_t is determined at each time step by an operating policy:

$$u_t = p(t, s_t) \quad (6)$$

and the state of the system is the reservoir storage s_t , which is altered according to the transition function described in equation 3). The sequence of states over the time horizon defines a system trajectory, which allows the evaluation of the performance of the operating policy p by means of the objective function defined in section 4.1.1. The optimal policy p^* is hence obtained by solving the following problem:

$$p^* = \arg \min_p J \quad (7)$$

The DP-family methods solve this optimisation problem by estimating the expected long-term cost of a policy for each state s_t , at time t by means of the value function, defined over a discrete grid of states and decisions:

$$H_t(s_t) = \min_{u_t} \Psi_{q_{t+1}} [\Phi_t(g_t(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1}), H_{t+1}(s_{t+1}))] \quad (8)$$

where $g_t(\cdot)$ is the time separable immediate cost function associated to the transition from state s_t to state s_{t+1} under the decision u_t . The modelling assumptions required by SDP for its application are finite domains of state, decision, and disturbance variables, time-separability of objective functions and constraints. These relatively mild assumptions imply, in theory, wide applicability of SDP to many problems, but in practice, its adoption is challenged by three curses (dimensionality, modelling, and multiple objectives) that considerably limit its use in complex real-life problems (Giuliani et al., 2016).

The computational cost of SDP grows exponentially with the state vector dimensionality, a feature referred to as the curse of dimensionality (Bellman 1957). Acceptable computational times are associated with a dimension of the state vector of 2 or 3, while for larger state vectors, SDP results inapplicable (Loucks et al. 2017). In addition, particularly in large systems, the disturbances are likely to be temporally correlated, and accounting for temporal correlation requires the use of a dynamic stochastic model, which contributes additional state variables and exacerbates the curse of dimensionality. The curse of modelling refers to the SDP requirement that any information included in the SDP framework must be explicitly modelled to predict the one-step-ahead model transition and, ultimately the value function (Tsitsiklis and Van Roy 1996). The implication of the curse of modelling is that no exogenous information can be added to the model unless it is turned into a state variable of a dynamic model (adding to the curse of dimensionality) or a stochastic time-independent disturbance. Finally, the curse of multiple objectives (Powell 2007) is related to those problems where the presence of multiple conflicting objectives requires generating a set of non-dominated alternatives, i.e., a Pareto front. The full set of Pareto-optimal solutions supports a posteriori decision-making by allowing the decision-maker to explore the key alternatives that compose system trade-offs and providing them with a broader context where their preferences can evolve and be exploited opportunistically (Woodruff, Reed, and Simpson 2013). Most of the DP-family methods rely on single-objective optimisation algorithms. Their application to multi-objective problems requires the use of a scalarisation function to reduce the dimensionality of the objective space to a single-objective problem (Chankong and Haimes 1983; Reville and McGarity 1997). The single-objective optimisation is then repeated for every Pareto-optimal point generated by using different scalarisation values (Soncini-Sessa, Weber, and Castelletti 2007). This process can be computationally very intensive in many-objective optimisation problems. Moreover, the Pareto front approximation loses in accuracy given the non-linear relationships between the scalarisation values and the corresponding objectives values.

The three curses of SDP limit its application in complex systems, therefore, over the years, a number of alternative methods have emerged, seeking to overcome one or more of these curses. Among these approaches, (i) **value-function-based methods** contrast the curse of dimensionality by computing an approximation of the value function (Bertsekas and Tsitsiklis 1995) that requires a sparser discretisation grid; (ii) **online methods** instead rely on the sequential resolution of multiple open-loop problems defined over a finite receding horizon (Bertsekas 2005)

addressing the curse of modelling. These two approaches, however, still require the estimation of the value function and its optimisation is still carried out as a single-objective problem; (iii) **policy-search-based methods** that make use of a simulation-based optimisation to iteratively improve the operating policies based on the simulation outcome (Marbach and Tsitsiklis 2001). This latter, generally named Direct Policy Search (DPS) (Rosenstein and Barto 2001), has been recently extended to solve multi-objective problems by using Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs), resulting in a viable option to address all three curses of SDP (Giuliani et al., 2016).

4.3.1 Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search

Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search (EMODPS) replaces the traditional SDP approach based on the computation of the value function with a simulation-based optimisation that directly operates in the policy space. EMODPS first parameterise the operating policy p_θ within a given family of functions and then, explores the parameter space θ seeking the best parameterisation of the operating policy with respect to the expected long-term cost defined by the objectives of the problem, i.e.:

$$p_\theta^* = \underset{p_\theta}{\operatorname{arg\,min}} J_{p_\theta} \quad \text{s.t. } \theta \in \Theta; \quad s_{t+1} = f_t(s_t, u_t, q_{t+1}) \quad (9)$$

where the vector of objective functions' components is described in paragraph 4.1.1.

Finding p_θ^* corresponds to finding the best parameters θ^* for the class of policy p_θ , measured by the objectives J_{p_θ} . A schematisation of the EMODPS algorithm is reported in Figure 31.

Figure 31: Schematisation of the Evolutionary Multi-Objective Direct Policy Search (EMODPS) approach; dashed lines represent the model of the system, and the grey box represents the MOEA algorithm (Giuliani et al., 2016).

Because of the simulation-based nature of EMODPS, the variables domain does not need to be discretised, overcoming at once the curse of dimensionality and the biases introduced by the discretisation of continuous variables (Baxter and Bartlett 2001). Moreover, it is possible to couple DPS with exogenous information or models, thus avoiding the curse of modelling (Giuliani et al. 2016; Denaro et al. 2017). Finally, the use of MOEAs resolves to curse of multi-objective as EMODPS algorithms allow to produce an approximation of the Pareto front in a single run for up to 10 objectives (Giuliani et al., 2014).

4.3.2 Evolutionary multi-objective direct policy search

4.3.2.1 Policy structure

EMODPS resolves a problem of parameters optimisation for a given policy structure. It can therefore find, at most, the best possible solution for the chosen class of functions. When the system to be optimised is already operating,

it is possible to infer the policy structure from the available data, although the water managers may not have operated at full attainable efficiency. If the system is under construction, neither data nor experience is available, and the policy structure must be guessed a priori on the basis of empirical considerations. The choice of a function with limited flexibility can thus restrict the search to a subspace of policies that, likely, does not contain the optimal one. It is hence advisable to select a very flexible class of functions, depending on a larger number of parameters, to ensure the possibility of approximating the unknown optimal solution of the problem to any desired degree of accuracy. Usually, the selected functions are universal approximating networks (for a review, see Tikk et al., 2003 and references therein). Two widely used non-linear universal approximators are artificial neural networks (ANNs) and radial basis functions (RBFs) (Zoppoli et al., 2002). It has been shown that any continuous function defined on a closed and bounded set can be approximated by three-layered ANNs (Cybenko 1989; Funahashi 1989) and three-layered RBFs (Chen and Chen 1995; Park and Sandberg 1991).

Although ANNs are more popular in the field of water management than RBFs, a comparative analysis carried out in the Red River basin (Giuliani et al., 2016) shows the general superiority of RBF on ANN for the problem of parameterisation of the operating policy. RBF policies computed for different time horizons consistently score better performances within a more reliable framework, i.e., without requiring any tuning or preconditioning of the policy design process. RBF thus represent an effective, case study-independent option for solving EMODPS problems and are therefore chosen as the universal approximation network for this study.

The RBF policy can be defined as follows:

$$u_t = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \varphi_i(I_t) + a \quad (10)$$

where N is the number of RBFs $\varphi(\cdot)$ and w_i are the weight of the i -th RBF. A single RBF is defined as

$$\varphi_i(I_t) = \exp \left[- \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{[(I_t)_j - c_{j,i}]^2}{b_{j,i}^2} \right] \quad (11)$$

where M is the number of policy inputs I_t and c_i , b_i are the M-dimensional centre and radius vectors of the i -th RBF, respectively. The centres of the RBF must lie within the bounded input space, and the radii must strictly be positives i.e., using normalised variables, $c_i \in [-1, 1]$ and $b_i \in (0, 1]$. The parameter vector θ is therefore defined as $\theta = [a, c_{i,j}, b_{i,j}, w_i]$ with $i = 1, \dots, N$, $j = 1, \dots, M$, and it belongs to R^{n_θ} , where $n_\theta = N(2M + nu) + 1$.

4.3.2.2 Optimisation algorithm – Borg MOEA

The two main options for the optimisation step of the algorithm (the grey box in Figure 31) are gradient-based methods and global optimisation algorithms, such as MOEAs. Simple parameterisations with few parameters are usually coupled with gradient-based methods, while global optimisation algorithms are preferred when the number of parameters to optimise is high. MOEAs are iterative search algorithms that evolve a Pareto-approximate set of solutions by mimicking the randomised mating, selection, and mutation operations that occur in nature to drive the search for efficient solutions (Coello et al., 2007). MOEAs have been shown to adapt well to multi-objective problems characterised by multi-modality, non-linearity, stochasticity, and discreteness (see Maier et al. 2014 and references therein). MOEAs thus represent a promising alternative to gradient-based optimisation methods in solving complex multi-objective water reservoir problems. In addition, MOEAs were proven to better handle performance uncertainties than gradient-based methods (Busa-Fekete et al. 2014). EMODPS is characterised by a high-dimensional space of policy parameters, and non-linear, multi-objective functions. To perform the optimisation, we use the self-adaptive Borg Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm, which has been shown to be highly robust in solving multi-objective optimal control problems, where it met or exceeded the performance of other state-of-the-art MOEAs (Zatarain Salazar et al. 2016). Borg MOEA differs from traditional evolutionary algorithms because the application of these operators is not bound to a fixed probability of occurrence. Their employment is adaptively adjusted during the course of the optimisation, considering their ability to generate efficient solutions (Hadka and Reed 2013). Along with the auto-adaptive search, Borg MOEA features other two strategies to contrast the main shortcomings of evolutionary algorithms: overfitting and poor exploration of the whole space when the search is trapped in a local minimum. The first strategy, the so-called ϵ -box dominance

archive, divides the optimisation space into hyper-boxes with side-length equal to ϵ . Pareto efficient solutions are searched into each box, ensuring convergence. ϵ -box dominance also supports the second strategy: time continuation. Time continuation ensures a global search of the space by injecting mutated solutions in each ϵ -box. Stagnation in a local minimum is prevented with internal algorithmic operators that detect search stagnation and randomly restart to escape local optima. Borg MOEA has been shown to outperform 9 benchmark evolutionary algorithms in terms of the number of solutions returned, ability to handle many-objective problems, ease-of-use, and overall consistency across a suite of challenging multi-objective problems (Reed et al. 2013).

5 Results

5.1 Experiment design

The system's simulation makes use of a historical scenario defined by:

- Agricultural and industrial water demands;
- inflows to the reservoirs and from the natural springs;
- Drinking water demand and aqueduct operating costs (required for Aquator simulation).

The considered 10-year simulation horizon covers the period from 01/01/2010 to 31/12/2019 at a daily time step. To avoid numerical issues, we considered a sub-daily integration step of two hours.

As explained in the previous Chapter, the operating policy belongs to the class of non-convex RBF. Due to the high computational effort required by the task, we defined a priori the number of units in the policy hidden layer to 14, following the rule of thumb (number of hidden units, 14 = number of inputs, 7, + number of outputs, 6, + 1) suggested in the literature for complex water system management tasks.

Table 7 reports the optimization setting adopted for the multi-objective search.

Table 7: Borg MOEA optimization setting.

Borg parameter	Numerical value
Number of initial random seeds	10
Number of function evaluations	250,000
Number of optimization variables	298
Number of objectives	4
ϵ values	0.1 (squared irrigation deficit) 0.001 (squared industrial deficit) 0.1 (drinking deficit) 0.5 (AQP distribution cost)

Note that the ϵ values reported in the last row of the table are the dimensions of the ϵ boxes (presented in the previous chapter) along each objective. These values have been set taking into account the variability range of each objective and performing an accurate trial-and-error analysis.

5.2 Numerical results

The core result of the analysis¹⁰ is the Pareto front of Figure 32 using a parallel axes plot representation. It allows to visualize the trade-off between the four considered objectives, all to be minimized, and considering relative values between 0 (best) to 1 (worst): irrigation, industrial, drinking deficits (first, second and third vertical axes) and potable water distribution cost (fourth axis). Note that the utopia point, whose coordinates are the best value that can be obtained for each objective individually, would be a horizontal line linking the lower value of each axis (0 in our rescaled visualization) in the parallel plot. As suggested by its name, this point is not practically reachable due

¹⁰ It should be noted that the results were obtained by simulating the institutional model that AQPspa uses internally to simulate its supply, purification, and distribution network. Due to a major version change, this model is still in the process of calibration and refinement. Furthermore, the simulations were fed with incomplete data and, in some cases, of modest quality. The results are therefore intended to be provisional and subject to correction: we reserve the right to persevere with data requests to the water authorities and agencies in charge, and to make close comparisons with AQPspa in order to improve the results.

to the trade-off between the objectives, but it serves as a reference point to guide the negotiation between the stakeholders to select a suitable compromise policy.

Figure 32: Graphical representation of the trade-off between the four considered objectives. The numerical values of the objectives reported in the parallel plot are rescaled between 0 and 1, corresponding to the extreme values (minimum and maximum) found in the optimization process. All the objectives have to be minimized. The black line indicates the compromise policy.

As expected, the parallel plot shows that the four objectives are highly competing. The trade-off between the three deficits (agricultural, industrial, and drinking) is due to the fact that the three users would make use of the same water resources coming from shared reservoirs. Due to the water scarcity regime in the region at hand, the water volume available is not sufficient to satisfy all the water demands at the same time, leading to a competitive situation. Consistently, the parallel plot shows that the policies that guarantee a low deficit for one of the water users do not produce satisfying values for the other competing sectors. The trade-off is particularly critical between the two main users in terms of the amount of water demanded: the agricultural districts and the aqueduct. The management policies in green give low values for the drinking deficit but high values for the agricultural deficit (the opposite situation occurs for the policies in red).

The figure shows the same pattern also for the last two axes: drinking deficit can be reduced only by increasing the economic cost related to the water distribution (including pumping, potabilization, ...) because, within certain limits, the lack of surface water can be compensated for by withdrawals from the aquifer, a generally more expensive solution.

As a compromise policy, we selected the one represented by the black line in Figure 32. The three water deficits have been prioritized in order to reflect the stakeholders' concerns. In this context, it is important to note that the drinking water distribution cost is covered by the bills paid by the final users (e.g., the citizens), an element that is not considered in our analysis.

To understand the impact of the selected system operation policy, we present and discuss the temporal dynamics of:

- the levels of each reservoir;
- the irrigation and industrial water deficits for each district;
- the drinking water deficit (aggregated for the whole distribution system);
- the potable water distribution cost.

Figure 33 reports the annual pattern of the levels for the five reservoirs. The level of each day of the year has been obtained by averaging the values for that day in the 10-year horizon between 2010 and 2019.

Figure 33: Trajectories of the reservoirs' level (average for the time horizon 2010-2019).

All the reservoirs present the same periodic pattern: the water inflows during winter time (a period of null agricultural demands and low drinking demand) are stored in the reservoirs reaching high water levels during spring. The combined effect of low inflows and high water demands causes a decrease in the reservoirs' level till October/November. At that point, the levels start increasing again during winter due to the process described above.

Figure 34 reports the time series of the irrigation (top 5 panels) and industrial (bottom panel) water deficit for each district. The results of the simulation show that a null irrigation water deficit for the entire horizon is obtained only in the case of the Locone reservoir.

Figure 34: Time series of the irrigation (top five panels) and industrial (bottom panel) water deficits in the considered districts.

In the considered 10-year time horizon, 2012 and 2017 represent two cases of extremely dry years. The effect of these droughts can be easily spotted in the deficit trajectory of Occhito and Pertusillo. Their deficit is quite low, with the only exceptions of 2012 (for Occhito) and 2017 (for Pertusillo). Interestingly, the considered policy seems to be able to distribute the deficit between these two districts using a sort of coordination mechanism, thanks to the possibility of partially compensating for the availability of water for drinking. In this way, at least partially, it is possible to free up resources for irrigation use.

In general, the irrigation district served by Conza reservoir emerges as the most vulnerable to droughts. Its deficit under the selected operating policy is not negligible even in particularly wet years and is exacerbated in critically dry years (i.e., 2012 and 2017).

Monte Cotugno reservoir is the only one distributing water to all the considered sectors, i.e., irrigation, industrial and potable. The pattern recorded for the industrial deficit is low in the first part of the simulation and worsen starting from 2017. This is even more evident looking at the irrigation deficit: it is almost negligible until 2016, while severe water shortages are registered from the following year.

Figure 35 reports the time series of the drinking water deficit produced on the horizon. It can be noticed that the periodic dynamic is quite constant with respect to one of irrigation and industrial deficits reported in Figure 34. In other words, the policy is able to reduce the effect of exceptionally dry years, exploiting alternative water sources (i.e., the wells).

Figure 35: Time series of the potable water deficit in the Apulia region (overall value across the whole system).

Small variations with respect to the standard periodic behaviour can be seen only in case the overall conditions of the system are consistently different from the average as in 2017.

The limited variations across different years in terms of water deficit reported in Figure 35 are in accordance with the constant trajectory shown in Figure 36 for the annual distribution cost sustained by AQP. The average cost for the considered horizon is about 55 M€ per year.

Figure 36: Drinking water distribution cost (annual values).

Exploring the Pareto front of Figure 32, we would be able to find policies that are much more efficient in minimizing the water distribution cost: some of them allow to reduce the cost to less than 30 M€. However, due to the strong conflict between drinking deficit and distribution cost, this would lead to an unacceptable drinking deficit.

6 Discussion and conclusion

We provide an in-depth description of the water resources scheme utilized by AQP, including in the analysis not only the drinking water use, but also other sectors (i.e., irrigation and industry) supplied by the same 5-reservoir system. This system is extremely complex under both the structural and administrative perspectives. The strategic reservoirs are interconnected by a wide network, composed by many hydraulic infrastructures such as pipelines, splitting and diversion nodes and water intakes. In addition, the high number of authorities that operates the infrastructures and has the responsibility of data acquisition, and of stakeholders affected by the water management strategies make it extremely challenging to provide a complete and coherent description of the system. Despite the presence of these critical issues, we successfully implemented a simulation model that can be used to estimate the effect of a considered management strategy in terms of potable water distribution cost and water deficit relative to drinking, industrial and agricultural demands. This latter has been individually computed for each irrigation sub-district pertaining to each reservoir, and then aggregated into one indicator, representative of the sector for the entire system.

Following the EMODPS framework, we nested the simulation model into an optimization tool, namely a genetic algorithm, that allowed to identify efficient operation policies for managing the whole system. In the present framework, the policy is identified in the hypothesis that a single water authority can coordinate the water releases from all the storage to reach a compromise solution synthetizing the competing need of the different users. However, this hypothesis somehow represents an ideal situation that does not fully coincide with reality. Indeed, at the beginning of each irrigation season, a negotiation takes place between stakeholders and water authorities to coordinate the reservoirs' operations so that a reasonable compromise can be reached.

Despite the complexity of the system and the high number of actors involved (institutions, authorities and stakeholders), the results obtained show that efficient compromise strategies exist. The proposed framework thus represents a consistent improvement with respect to the current management adopted by AQP at least in two directions: it extends the mathematical model of the system including other stakeholders (i.e., industry and agriculture), and adopts a more advanced and robust optimization tool. This is, however, a partial result that should be substantially improved considering the following points:

1. It is still necessary to consolidate and check with the water authorities some basic information, such as the irrigation water demand of some districts and the water balance in some reservoirs.
2. The reduced model of the aqueduct needs to be recalibrated considering the improved implementation in Aquator which will be developed in the next months by AQP spa.
3. The baseline has to be re-evaluated considering the aforementioned improvements, and the new results checked for consistency involving water authorities and irrigation districts.
4. Once the consolidated version of the baseline will be available, the results will be extended by considering climate and socio-economic projections to properly consider future scenarios.
5. We will evaluate the effect of adopting innovative water-saving strategies by partially replacing the traditional sources considered in the baseline with unconventional ones closing local water-loops. In particular, we will assess the effectiveness of these solutions both within the aqueduct, considering the reactivation of wells for emergency use, and the irrigation districts, by using refinement water which could partially decrease the water demands.
6. Structural improvements in the AQP water distribution system can be implemented. Note that, these improvements would be in line with the investment plan of AQP spa and are relative to actions already at an advanced stage.

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Appendix – Drought characterization

Drought is one of the deadliest natural hazards (Lloyd-Hughes, 2014) because of its potentially destructive impacts on agriculture, ecological environment, and socioeconomic systems. Droughts occur when precipitation is lower than expected or lower than normal and this, protracted over a season or longer period, involves the inability to satisfy the human demand and environment needs (WMO, 2006). Due to its complex nature, a universal criterion for what constitutes a drought is still an open issue. Instead, multiple definitions, indexes, and metrics exist reflecting the different needs of research communities or applications (Ault, 2020). Furthermore, the achievement of a precise definition is hindered by differences in hydrometeorological variables, socioeconomic factors, but also in the stochastic nature of water demands around the world (Mishra and Singh, 2010).

Drought and Water Scarcity

Drought is the least understood phenomenon among all natural hazards, affecting more people than any other hazard (Wilhite, 1993). Hurricanes, for example, have a definite beginning and can easily be seen as they develop and move. On the other hand, drought is a creeping phenomenon that slowly sneaks up, hitting many sectors and operating over many different time scales (Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2021). A unanimous and precise definition of drought is still missing. However, some common definitions of this concept are given by (i) The World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 1986) stating that "drought means a sustained, extended deficiency in precipitation"; (ii) The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 1983) that defines a drought hazard as "the percentage of years when crops fail from the lack of moisture"; (iii) Palmer (1965), who described a "drought as a significant deviation from the normal hydrological conditions of an area". All these definitions are valid in defining the concept of drought, but they refer to different variables and development stages. The first definition characterizes drought through precipitation, the second one employs the state of the crop, and the latter considers the streamflow in the hydrological cycle. As a multiscale phenomenon, it is fundamental to take into account the time scale over which water deficits accumulate (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). For this reason, we can distinguish three types of droughts:

- **Meteorological drought** is defined as a lack of precipitation over a region for a period of time (Mishra and Singh, 2010). The longer and the more spatially extensive the precipitation deficiency is, the more likely different types of droughts will occur (Spinoni et al., 2016). This type of drought is often accompanied by above-normal temperatures and can be exacerbated by low relative humidity, or strong and persisting desiccating winds (Lei and Duan, 2011). Since it precedes and causes the other types of droughts (Dai, 2011), meteorological drought is often regarded as the key type of drought that takes place in the short term (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010).
- **Agricultural drought**. This type of drought accounts for and is defined through, the state of the crop. As in the previously reported definition by FAO, it is associated with water stress and a reduction in biomass and production due to a deficiency of water in the root zone. When it takes place, it usually develops in the medium term (Pedro-Monzonís et al., 2015).
- **Hydrological drought** is usually characterized by water loss over time from both underground and surface supplies. It usually affects water levels from average to low, making it inadequate to meet human and ecosystem requirements. Streamflow is the most crucial variable that expresses the availability of water in the water cycle. Recovery from hydrological drought is usually prolonged, considering the time it takes to recharge streams and lakes (Hasan et al., 2019; WMO, 2006).
- **Operational drought**. The local water balance highlights that a universal description of drought requires reference to water supply, demand, and management; through water management, human intervention influences the definition of the drought itself in the universal sense, and it can only be removed in the case of purely meteorological drought (Van Loon et al., 2016). Therefore, a dry spell may be originated by the natural scarcity of precipitation as well as excessive use of water resources, particularly in highly regulated contexts. This is the reason why there is also the need to introduce the concept of Operational Drought.

This fourth type of drought is socio-economic, and it is associated with water resource systems failing to meet water demands (Khan et al., 2018). Operational drought derives from the combination of lack of water resources

(hydrological drought), and excess demand. Moreover, its effect can be further worsened by an inadequate design and management of the water exploitation system and its operating rules (Mishra and Singh, 2010).

Operational drought triggers Water Scarcity. Water scarcity is defined as the shortage of water resources to satisfy water demands in the long term. This means that the demand for water exceeds the resources exploitable under sustainable conditions. Among the concurring causes, there could be other non-meteorological factors, such as lack of water supply or transport systems, excess of demands or their mutual incompatibility, and constraints for water management (water rights, floods, see Martin-Carrasco and Garrote, 2006). Every continent is already affected by water scarcity, and an ever-growing number of regions are reaching the limit such that water services can no longer be sustainably delivered, especially in arid regions (UN, 2021).

Drought Impacts

Drought is a multifaceted natural hazard impacting ecosystems and society in many ways (Van Loon et al., 2016) and produces a complex web of impacts that ripple through many spheres of environment, economy, and society (Wilhite et al., 2007; Blauhut et al., 2015). Assessing the impacts of droughts is fundamental to providing critical information to support rational decisions, which will turn into mitigation policies and programs (Ding et al., 2011). According to the Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT), more than one billion people were affected by droughts in the period 1995-2015; that is more than a quarter of all people affected by all types of weather-related disasters worldwide (CRED, 2015). However, due to the lack of a univocal methodology, drought impact-related data are continuously revised; still, more than half of all deaths linked with natural hazards are classified as drought-related (Below et al., 2007). This is because they are associated with widespread agricultural failures, loss of livestock, water shortages, and outbreaks of epidemic diseases. As an additional consequence, many people around the world are food insecure and large sections of the population are forced to displace (CRED, 2015). JRC PESETA IV (2020) (Projection of Economic impacts of climate change in Sectors of the EU based on bottom-up Analysis) estimates current annual losses from drought to be around 9 billion e for the EU and UK, with the highest losses in the Mediterranean Basin. Besides, environmental impacts on these areas are difficult to quantify and consider (Cammalleri et al., 2020). These impacts may be experienced well outside the affected region, extending even to the global scale. The complexity of impacts is largely caused by the dependence of so many sectors on the water for producing goods and providing services (Wilhite et al., 2007). In order to provide a clearer picture, impacts from drought can be classified as direct or indirect. Reduced crop, rangeland, and forest productivity; increased fire hazard; reduced water levels; increased livestock and wildlife mortality rates; and damage to wildlife and fish habitat are a few examples of direct impacts. The consequences of these impacts are classified as indirect impacts. For example, a reduction in the crop, rangeland, and forest productivity may result in reduced income for farmers and agribusiness, increased prices for food and timber, unemployment, reduced government tax revenues because of decreased expenditures, increased crime, foreclosures on bank loans to farmers and businesses, migration, and disaster relief programs. The indirect losses associated with drought often exceed direct losses. Many sectors are involved, different areas are affected, numerous environmental damages and personal hardships should be considered. Furthermore, losses are also quite variable from one drought to another in the same location, depending on the timing, intensity, and spatial extent of the event. Therefore, the quantification of the financial costs of droughts is a formidable challenge (Wilhite et al., 2007).

Drought Trends

There is an established consensus about recent trends of droughts in Europe: in the last decades, southern Europe experienced increasing drought frequency and severity with the Mediterranean and the Carpathian Regions as hotspots. Northern Europe, on the other hand, showed a trend to wetter conditions (Spinoni et al., 2018). In a climate change scenario, drought impacts could become more impacting, and it is thus fundamental to identify areas where droughts are projected to become more frequent and severe. Ongoing global warming is fueling a change in drought frequency and intensity. Hydrological droughts will progressively happen more frequently, last longer, and become more intense in southern and western parts of Europe, while drought conditions will become

less extreme in northern and north-eastern Europe. The 1.5 °C global warming limit would result in an increase of drought frequency over 2/3 of the Mediterranean Region and 1/3 over the Atlantic Region, but this scenario would still avoid a doubling of drought frequency everywhere in Europe. With 3°C global warming in 2100 drought losses could be 5 times higher compared to today, with the strongest increase in drought losses projected in the Mediterranean and Atlantic regions of Europe. Figure 37 shows how the frequency is going to change with respect to an area and a global warming scenario (Cammalleri et al., 2020).

Figure 37: Fraction of area exposed to changes in drought occurrence for European sub-regions

In conclusion, climate change is expected to emphasize the disequilibrium between European Northern Regions and the Mediterranean Basin water balance through changes in the spatial and temporal distribution of precipitation and, therefore, more frequent and severe dry spells in Southern Europe.

Drought Indexes

In order to provide decision-makers useful tools, a variety of indicators has been developed to fulfil specific needs. In this Section, an exploration of the main drought indexes is reported.

Definitions and applications

Due to the increasing frequency and severity of droughts, the interest in investigating this complex natural hazard is growing. Those phenomena are common throughout the world with devastating damage potential on agriculture, economy, and society (Niemeyer et al., 2008). Consequently, considerable efforts have been devoted to drought monitoring, prediction, and risk analysis (Hao et al., 2017). To reduce the damages from droughts, it is crucial to characterize them. Drought characterization permits enhanced preparation and contingency planning, facilitating operations such as early warning and drought risk analysis (Zargar et al., 2011). The usage of a drought index is fundamental to detect and monitor a drought (Niemeyer et al., 2008), declare the beginning of the end of a drought period (Tsakiris et al., 2007), allow drought managers to declare drought levels, and instigate adequate response measures (Zargar et al., 2011), evaluate drought severity (Niemeyer et al., 2008), facilitate the communication of drought conditions among various interested entities (Zargar et al., 2011) and many more purposes. Drought indexes can be defined as quantitative measures that characterize drought levels by integrating data from one or several variables (e.g. precipitation, evapotranspiration) into a single numerical value. This procedure brings us to a more useful and interpretable tool with respect to raw indicator data. Drought indexes depict different events and conditions, namely climate dryness anomalies, mainly based on precipitation, or delayed agricultural and hydrological impacts such as soil moisture loss or lowered reservoir levels. In addition, the categorization of drought indexes can also be based on the data and technology used. For example, a considerable number of indices use remote-sensing imagery to detect vegetation health as an indicator of drought (Zargar et al., 2011).

Over time, more than 150 indices have been developed (Niemeyer et al., 2008) but in the following sections, only the most relevant and renowned will be presented since an exhaustive analysis goes beyond the scope of this work.

Indexes of Drought as a natural Hazard

A first main indexes classification follows the scheme of drought classification introduced in the previous section that distinguishes between meteorological, agricultural, and hydrological drought.

The first generation of drought indexes relied primarily on meteorological variables, mainly precipitation; for this reason, they are classified as meteorological drought indexes (Niemeyer et al., 2008), since this type of droughts is triggered by a lack of precipitation.

Agricultural drought can be monitored by assessing soil moisture content levels and evapotranspiration. However, direct soil moisture data measurement is not always available at regional and basin scales. To estimate soil moisture content, process-based models may be used (Wambua, 2019). Some other common ways to assess the state of the crop is by remote sensing-derived information, this family of indexes is presented in the following.

Another class of drought indexes has been developed in the hydrological domain (Niemeyer et al., 2008). From the water-cycle perspective, hydrology-oriented drought indexes have been developed to characterize the comprehensive picture of the water balance in a catchment area for water management purposes (Niemeyer et al., 2008). The main variable is streamflow, but more comprehensive indicators can also include snowpack extent, reservoir storage, and groundwater level (Zargar et al., 2011).

Despite the seemingly straightforward distinction, most of these indexes do not easily fit into the description of a single drought type (Zaniolo, 2017) as the phenomenon considered is complex and multifaceted and the borders of each drought category are labile. An alternative classification of drought indexes can be structured by looking at the procedures and the data needed for computing the indicators, distinguishing between model-based indexes, statistical indexes, remote sensing-based indexes, and combined indexes (See Table 6).

Table 8: Table of Indexes of Drought as Natural Hazard.

Computation class	Index	Required Input
Model-based Indexes	PDSI	Precipitation, Temperature
	SMDI, ETDI	Precipitation, Temperature
Statistical Indexes	EDI	Precipitation
	SWSI	Precipitation, Streamflow, Reservoir Storage, Snow Pack
	ADI	Precipitation, Streamflow, Reservoir Storage, Soil Moisture, SWE
	SPI	Precipitation
	SMRI	Precipitation, Snow Melt
	SPEI	Precipitation, Evapotranspiration
	SRI	Streamflow
	SSI	Soil Moisture
	SWI	Reservoir level
	Remote Sensing-Derived Indexes	NDVI
NDWI		NIR and SWIR channels
LST		TIR channels
Combined Indexes	HDI	SPI, PDSI, SWSI
	MSDI	SPI, SSI
	TVX	LST, NDVI
	PPVI	SPI, VHI
	NDDI	NDVI, NDWI
	VegDRI	NDVI, SPI, PDSI
	VHI	NDVI, LST

Model-based Indexes

Model-based indexes rely on a hydrological model to describe the water content and flow of the region under study (Zaniolo, 2017). The type of model and its level of complexity depending on the aim of the indicator. It must be noted that a very complex model will require a relevant amount of data in calibration, so the accuracy of these indexes is directly linked to data availability and quality (Narasimhan and Srinivasan, 2005).

Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI)

Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI) is a meteorological drought index formulated in the 1960s to evaluate prolonged periods of both extraordinary wet and unusually dry weather conditions using more than just precipitation data (Narasimhan and Srinivasan, 2005).

To capture the intensity, end, and beginning of drought (Alley, 1984), this method relies upon a primitive water balance (Wells et al., 2004) between soil moisture supply and demand (Palmer, 1965b) and it uses precipitation and temperature as inputs for estimating moisture supply and demand within a two-layer soil model (Mishra and Singh, 2010). PDSI method is used around the world and this methodology is robust in identifying droughts since it uses soil data and a total water balance. However, PDSI comes with some drawbacks: (i) the arbitrariness of soil layers and the fixed value of the available water capacity; (ii) the snowmelt and frozen precipitation across the western region are not considered. Furthermore, many parameters used in the PDSI are sensitive to the calibration procedures (Mo, 2008). Despite these limitations, PDSI is still one of the most popular indexes in literature.

Soil Moisture Deficit Index (SMDI) and Evapotranspiration Deficit Index (ETDI)

As precipitation and soil properties have a high degree of spatial variability, Soil Moisture Deficit Index (SMDI) and Evapotranspiration Deficit Index (ETDI) have been developed as two complementary indicators to describe meteorological and agricultural drought using as inputs precipitation and temperature. Those indicators operate at a much finer spatial resolution than PDSI using a comprehensive hydrologic model coupled with a crop growth model and Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The consideration of spatial variability of hydrological parameters related to soil type and land cover and meteorological parameters such as rainfall and temperature is a better approximation of the hydrologic system and improves the ability to monitor soil moisture deficit at a much better spatial resolution (Narasimhan and Srinivasan, 2005).

These indicators have a high potential in terms of applicability for different regions of the world and agricultural practices (Wambura, 2021) but they strongly rely on the calibration of parameters of complex hydrological models, which can reveal to be a difficult task due to the scarcity of reliable field measurement of key variables, such as soil moisture (Wambura, 2021; Zaniolo, 2017).

Statistical Indicators

One of the most intuitive, quick, and easy ways to determine drought is by comparing actual precipitation to a long-term average. In order to provide more information than just how the current situation compares with the historical average, scientists derived many statistical drought indicators (Yihdego et al., 2019) which rely on the statistical analysis of time series to find the anomalies that may lead to drought conditions (Zaniolo, 2017).

Generally, these indicators investigate the statistical distribution of time series and identify drought periods when the observed values are persistently and significantly below the normal condition (Mishra and Singh, 2011).

The main advantage of statistical indicators is their scalability across time and space. This feature allows drought severity at two or more locations to be compared with each other regardless of climatic differences between them (Morid et al., 2006), thus overcoming the main drawback typical of model-based indicators (Mishra and Singh, 2010).

One of the drawbacks of statistical indicators is that, to build a reliable probability distribution, typically records of at least 30 years of data are required, but not always available. It is worth noting that when the input variables are expensive or hard to measure, (e.g., evapotranspiration and soil moisture) a model is often employed prior to the computation of the statistical index to produce the necessary time series of inputs (Zaniolo, 2017).

Effective Drought Index (EDI)

The Effective Drought Index (EDI) was proposed by Byun and Wilhite (1999) and its original form employs daily rainfall data to assess drought severity and duration (Pandey et al., 2008).

EDI is defined as the objective measure of daily water accumulation based on the weight of the current and antecedent rainfall (Malik et al., 2021).

Compared to other drought indices, the EDI has several advantages. First, it is the only index that was specifically designed to calculate daily drought severity. This enables rapid detection of drought and precise measurement of

short-term drought. Furthermore, by utilizing a calculation method that places greater emphasis on recent precipitation, it more accurately calculates the current level of available water resources (Kim et al., 2009).

EDI is often preferred as it is more effective in the identification of drought features (i.e., initiation, termination, and duration) and it needs only rainfall data of more than 30-year periods for drought estimation. (Malik et al., 2021).

Surface Water Supply Index (SWSI)

One of the most well-known indices of hydrologic drought is the Surface Water Supply Index (SWSI). Rainfall, snow, streamflow, and reservoir storage levels are required as inputs for the index to be calculated (Aghelpour et al., 2021).

Shafer and Dezman (1982) designed the SWSI to be an indicator of surface water conditions and described the index as a mountain water-dependent, in which mountain snowpack is a major component. The objective of the SWSI was to incorporate both hydrological and climatological features into a single index value. These values would be standardized to allow comparisons between basins. Because it is dependent on the season, the SWSI is computed with only snowpack, precipitation, and reservoir storage in wintertime. During the summer months, streamflow replaces snowpack as a component within the SWSI equation (Kwon and Kim, 2006).

SWSI comes with some limitations. There is a lack of consensus over the definition of surface water supply; and the factor weights vary from state to state and, in some cases, from month to month, resulting in SWSIs with different statistical properties. (Heim Jr, 2002).

Aggregate Drought Index (ADI)

The Aggregate Drought Index (ADI) is a multivariate drought index that considers the bulk quantity of water across the meteorological, hydrological, and agricultural regimes of drought. The six parameters adopted for the ADI include precipitation, evapotranspiration, streamflow, reservoir storage, soil moisture content, and snow water content. These variables may be used selectively, depending on the characteristics of the region of interest. For instance, if a region does not possess a winter snowpack, snow should be omitted. Since the approach treats months separately, it is possible to use a different set of variables for each month.

The ADI comprehensively considers all physical forms of drought (meteorological, hydrological, and agricultural) through a selection of variables that are related to each drought type. Water stored in large surface water reservoirs was also included. Hydroclimatic monthly data for each climate division underwent correlation-based principal component analysis (PCA) (Keyantash and Dracup, 2004).

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)

The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) was designed by McKee et al. (1993) and it is a probability index that was developed to give a better representation of abnormal wetness and dryness than the Palmer indices (Guttman, 1999). This indicator measures anomalies of accumulated precipitation during a given period (e.g. 1, 3, 12 months), and is the most commonly used indicator for detecting and characterizing meteorological droughts (European Drought Observatory, 2021). For the calculation of SPI, a long-term precipitation record is needed, and a theoretical distribution has to be chosen. The SPI has often been calculated based on the Gamma distribution, even though some authors claim that other distributions like the Pearson type III distribution might be more suitable (Staudinger et al., 2014; Guttman, 1999). The chosen probability distribution is then transformed to a normal distribution so that the mean SPI for the location and desired period is zero (McKee et al., 1993; Mishra and Singh, 2010). As a result, positive SPI values indicate greater than mean precipitation and negative values indicate less than mean precipitation (Morid et al., 2006) and the magnitude of the departure from zero is a probabilistic measure of the severity of a wet or dry event that can be used for risk assessment (Guttman, 1999). Some of the advantages of these indicators are that SPI is simple, spatially invariant in its interpretations, and probabilistic so that it can be used in risk and decision analysis, and it also can be tailored to time periods of concern to a user (Guttman, 1999). For example, short-term durations on the order of months (or even weeks) may be important to agricultural interests while very long-term durations spanning years may be important to water supply management interests. SPI versatility allows monitoring short-term water supplies, such as soil moisture which is important for agricultural production, and long-term water resources, such as groundwater supplies, streamflow, and lake and reservoir levels. Soil moisture conditions respond to precipitation anomalies on a relatively short scale. Groundwater,

streamflow, and reservoir storage reflect the long-term precipitation anomalies (Mishra and Singh, 2010). It has to be noted that the length of the precipitation record and the nature of probability distribution plays an important role in calculating SPI (Mishra and Singh, 2010). The fact that SPI requires as input precipitation records only is considered an advantage because of its simplicity compared to other drought indices (Staudinger et al., 2014) but, on the other hand, it measures the precipitation deficits without taking into account water supply (Mo, 2008). Besides, temperature, evapotranspiration, snowmelt, and soil water capacity are other potentially relevant but overlooked variables.

Therefore, over the years several complementary drought indicators were developed substituting precipitation as variable but maintaining the SPI computational procedure. Examples of these indicators, along with their applications are:

- **Standardized Melt and Rain Index (SMRI)**. In snow-influenced catchments, snow has a dominant role in the water cycle. As an extension to the SPI, the Standardized Snow Melt and Rain Index (SMRI) has been introduced. If precipitation is temporarily stored as snow, there is a significant difference between meteorological and hydrological drought because of the delayed release of meltwater to the stream. The SMRI accounts for rain and snowmelt deficits, which effectively influence streamflow. This indicator employs the SPI procedure on an input time series composed of the sum of precipitation and snowmelt (Staudinger et al., 2014). The SMRI can be derived without snow data by indirectly estimating the snowmelt contributions from temperature and precipitation data (i.e., by setting a threshold temperature to model snow accumulation and melting).
- **Standardized Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)**. Since the SPI does not account for atmospheric conditions other than precipitation the Standardized Precipitation and Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) was proposed by Vicente-Serrano et al. (2010). Based on the principle of water balance, the SPEI uses the difference between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration as the input condition to evaluate the dry and wet conditions of the area (Pei et al., 2020; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). The greatest differences between SPEI and SPI occur during the summer when potential evapotranspiration represents a greater portion of the climatic water balance (Stagge et al., 2014). Furthermore, because SPEI accounts for evapotranspiration, it is more sensible to the state of the crops than indicators based only on precipitation Zaniolo (2017). Standardized Runoff Index (SRI) Hydrological drought is measured by streamflow or runoff deficits. Shukla and Wood (2008) applied the same concept of the SPI to analyze runoff data on different time scales. The SRI can be computed the same way as the SPI except it is based on the monthly-mean runoff time series (Mo, 2008).
- **Standardized Soil Moisture Index (SSI)**. The Standardized Soil Moisture Index (SSI) (Hao and AghaKouchak, 2013) is defined in a similar way to the commonly used SPI (McKee et al., 1993). In some studies, SSI has been used in a nonparametric form using the empirical probability of the historical soil moisture data (AghaKouchak, 2014). It is generally considered slower than SPI in detecting the onset of a drought, but it is more effective in assessing its persistence. Since it directly accounts for the state of the soil, SSI analyzes agricultural and hydrological drought, while it is not suitable to represent short-term meteorological conditions (Zaniolo, 2017).
- **Standardized Water level Index (SWI)**. For hydrological drought analysis, examination of streamflow statistics and run series analysis is the widely used technique (Bhuiyan, 2004). A Standardized Water-level Index (SWI) has been developed to assess groundwater recharge deficit. SWI accounts for anomalies in water levels with respect to the seasonal mean.

Remote Sensing-Derived Indicators

Historically, droughts have been mostly monitored and investigated using ground-based point observations or interpolated grids. Globally, however, many areas used for agricultural production are not well instrumented (e.g., at least one climate station per 5000 km²) to provide ground-based observations of precipitation, near-surface air temperature, wind speed, atmospheric water vapor, relative humidity, and atmospheric evaporative demand that are consistent over the long term (i.e., at least 30 years of observation) (AghaKouchak et al., 2015). In many other regions, the available observations are not sufficient to capture the spatiotemporal variability of drought-related variables such as precipitation. Furthermore, observations from different meteorological stations often have different record lengths and variable data quality (Easterling et al., 2016), which makes consistent global drought

analysis using ground-based observations challenging (AghaKouchak and Nakhjiri, 2012). The satellite or Remote Sensing (RS) indices involve the application of the science and art of obtaining information of points, objects, areas, or phenomena through analysis of data acquired by a sensor, which is not in direct physical contact with the target of investigation (Wambua, 2019). RS-derived images have been recently introduced to monitor the changes in vegetation cover to be employed as indicators of drought (Zaniolo, 2017). Vegetation responds structurally and physiologically (e.g., by reducing their leaf cover) to droughts to minimize the effects of water stress, and longer and more severe droughts can lead to lasting changes in canopy structure, often facilitated by disturbance events including wildfire and outbreaks of insect pests (AghaKouchak et al., 2015).

In recent years, various remote-sensing indices have been developed and can be employed in agricultural drought monitoring (Monteleone et al., 2020). While there are immense opportunities for supporting drought monitoring via remote sensing, there are major challenges including data continuity, unquantified uncertainty, sensor changes, and community acceptability, and the short length of available records (AghaKouchak et al., 2015). Several relevant satellite missions and sensors provide only a decade of data, which may not be sufficient to study droughts from a climate perspective (Liu et al., 2016). However, they still provide valuable information about relevant hydrologic and ecological processes linked to this natural hazard (AghaKouchak et al., 2015).

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is one of the commonly used indicators to detect and indicate the status and dynamics of vegetation cover (Xing et al., 2020), and the first remote sensing-based measure used to monitor agricultural drought (AghaKouchak et al., 2015). Quantitative assessment of vegetation condition is generally based on the spectral signature of vegetation greenness expressed in the red and near-infrared (NIR) portions of the electromagnetic spectrum (AghaKouchak et al., 2015). Satellite remote sensors can quantify what fraction of the photosynthetically active radiation is absorbed by vegetation. Since green vegetation had strong absorption of spectrum in the red region and high reflectance in the infrared region, NDVI was thus formulated as a combination of red and infrared bands (Sruthi and Aslam, 2015).

$$NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{RED}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{RED}}$$

NDVI values thus range from -1 to +1, where negative values correspond to an absence of vegetation (Pettorelli et al., 2005). When analyzed through time, NDVI can reveal where vegetation is thriving and where it is under stress (USGS, 2021).

The main advantages of this index are the following: NDVI can be easily computed through a simple transformation of spectral bands; there are relatively long time series available (more than 20 years) (Eumetrain, 2021); it provides global coverage; and it has a very high spatial resolution (Monteleone et al., 2020). However, some disadvantages are the inherent nonlinearity because it is a ratio-based index (Eumetrain, 2021) and it has a lagged response to drought because of a lagged vegetation response to developing rainfall deficits due to residual moisture stored in the soil (Thenkabail and Gamage, 2004).

Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

Many vegetation stress and drought indicators have been developed using short-wave infrared (SWIR). One of the most famous is the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) (Gao, 1996). It is computed using the near-infrared (NIR) and the short-wave infrared (SWIR) reflectance, which makes it sensitive to changes in liquid water content and in the spongy mesophyll of vegetation canopies (Gao, 1996; Ceccato et al., 2001). Its usefulness for drought monitoring and early warning has been demonstrated in different studies (Ceccato et al., 2002).

Land Surface Temperature (LST)

Drought stress can also be quantified using remotely sensed surface brightness temperature derived from thermal channels (Gutman, 1999). The Land Surface Temperature (LST) computed from thermal infrared bands has been found to provide valuable information on surface moisture conditions (Gutman, 1990; AghaKouchak et al., 2015). The thermal data from satellite images are important because they allow the detection of interannual changes in surface moisture, when the change in the vegetation index fails to produce a significant signal (Gutman, 1990).

Combined Indexes

Several studies argue that drought monitoring efforts should be based on multiple variables/indicators to provide a more robust and integrated measure of drought that captures the diverse range of vegetation response to drought across different ecosystems (AghaKouchak et al., 2015). Defining droughts based on a single variable/index (e.g., precipitation, soil moisture, or runoff) may not be sufficient for reliable risk assessment and decision-making (Hao and AghaKouchak, 2013).

Hybrid Drought Index (HDI)

The Hybrid Drought Index (HDI) has been developed by combining the three important indices of meteorological, hydrological, and agricultural droughts, namely, the standardized precipitation index (SPI), the surface water supply index (SWSI), and the Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI). The data obtained from drought damage is a good indicator of combined drought severity and include all aspects of their gradual and longer-term impacts. Therefore, it can be used to identify the combined effects of drought and to analyze its variability to develop preventive schemes and reduce drought impacts on different water user sectors (Karamouz et al., 2009).

Multivariate Standardized Drought Index (MSDI)

This index probabilistically combines the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) and the Standardized Soil Moisture Index (SSI) for drought characterization using the concept of copula. In other words, MSDI incorporates the meteorological and agricultural drought conditions for an overall characterization of drought. The results reveal that MSDI indicates the drought onset and termination based on the combination of SPI and SSI, with onset being dominated by SPI and drought persistence being more like SSI behavior. Overall, MSDI is shown to be a reasonable model for combining probabilistically multiple indices (Hao and AghaKouchak, 2013).

Temperature-Vegetation Index (TVX)

The Temperature-Vegetation Index (TVX) is a combination of surface temperatures and spectral vegetation index measurements, namely as a ratio of LST and NDVI. TVX accounts for the variable influence of vegetation cover in soil moisture assessment (Goward et al., 2002). This index is useful when NDVI alone does not effectively represent the interannual variability of land cover (Zaniolo, 2017).

Probabilistic Precipitation Vegetation Index (PPVI)

The Probabilistic Precipitation Vegetation Index (PPVI) is a composite index that considers both meteorological drought through the SPI, and agricultural drought conditions by including the VHI, two consolidated indices. The PPVI is a powerful tool since it can identify events of vegetation stress, and at the same time, select among those the ones actually due to drought, thanks to the contemporary use of both VHI and SPI. As such, it can be helpful in agricultural drought monitoring and can be used to identify drought events affecting a region, their severity and their duration. One of the main advantages is that PPVI requires as inputs only precipitation and VHI, a remote-sensing drought index (Monteleone et al., 2020).

Normalized Difference Drought Index (NDDI)

The Normalized Difference Drought Index (NDDI) has been proposed as a combination of NDVI and NDWI (Gu et al., 2007). Sensitivity of NDWI and NDVI to drought conditions has been explored, revealing that combining information from visible, near infrared, and short-wave infrared channels improved sensitivity to drought severity (Gu et al., 2007). NDDI has a stronger response to summer drought conditions than a simple difference between NDVI and NDWI, and it is therefore a more sensitive indicator of drought in grasslands than NDVI alone (AghaKouchak et al., 2015).

Vegetation Drought Response Index (VegDRI)

The Vegetation Drought Response Index (VegDRI) integrates climate-based drought indices, satellite-based observations of vegetation conditions, and other biophysical information (e.g., land cover type, soil characteristics, and elevation) to describe the levels of vegetation drought stress (Brown et al., 2008). While NDVI is proven to provide valuable information on vegetation health, one may not be able to identify the root causes of vegetation stress solely from NDVI. The main reason is that many factors such as fire, land cover change, plant disease, pest infestation, biomass harvesting, and flooding can cause anomalies in NDVI like those caused by drought. To address this limitation, VegDRI incorporates climate-based data from SPI and the Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI) as

additional indicators of dryness and analyzes them in combination with satellite-based NDVI information (AghaKouchak et al., 2015).

Vegetation Health Index (VHI)

The Vegetation Health Index (VHI) is based on a combination of products extracted from vegetation signals, namely the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and from the brightness temperatures (Kogan, 1997; Karnieli et al., 2006). VHI provides, as NDVI, a measure of vegetation health and it can be used as a proxy to detect potential drought (FAO, 2021). One drawback of the VHI is the impossibility to identify the cause of the vegetation stress. In fact, vegetation can suffer because of various events: excessive wetness, pests, fires, droughts, or others. It is a biophysical indicator of a lack of precipitation but can also be seen as representing drought impacts on the ground (Monteleone et al., 2020).

Indicators of water scarcity

Indicators of water scarcity address the analysis of Operational droughts (Zaniolo, 2017). These indicators serve as a measure of the availability of safe and affordable water for human needs for drinking, washing or livelihoods (Rijsberman, 2006). Metrics of water scarcity and stress have evolved over the last three decades from simple threshold indicators to holistic measures characterizing human environments and freshwater sustainability. Metrics commonly estimate renewable freshwater resources using mean annual river runoff, which masks hydrological variability, and quantify subjectively socio-economic conditions characterizing adaptive capacity (Damkjaer and Taylor, 2017).

Water Stress Index (WSI)

Falkenmark and Lindh (1974) proposed one of the first quantitative links between freshwater resources and population at the Third World Population Conference in Bucharest in 1974 (Damkjaer and Taylor, 2017). Formal quantification of water scarcity began, however, in the early 1980s with the development of the Water Stress Index (WSI) explicitly linking food security to freshwater availability (Falkenmark et al., 1989; Damkjaer and Taylor, 2017): they proposed 1700 cubic meters of renewable water resources per capita per year as the threshold, based on estimates of water requirements in the household, agricultural, industrial and energy sectors, and the needs of the environment. The main advantages of this simple indicator are that the data are readily available, and its meaning is intuitive and easy to understand. As a result, the indicator dominates the popular discussion of water scarcity, even though its disadvantages are clear as well. These are the annual national averages that hide important scarcity at smaller scales. Moreover, the indicator does not consider the availability of infrastructure that modifies the availability of water to users and the simple thresholds do not reflect important variations in demand among countries due to, for instance, lifestyle, climate, etc. (Rijsberman, 2006).

Water Resources Vulnerability Index (WRVI)

Water Resources Vulnerability Index (WRVI) is defined as the total annual withdrawals as a percent of available water resources. Water withdrawals are defined as the amount of water taken out of rivers, streams, or groundwater aquifers to satisfy human needs for water. Raskin et al. (1997) suggest that a country is water scarce if annual withdrawals are between 20 and 40% of annual supply, and severely water scarce if this figure exceeds 40%. Alcamo et al. (1997) also use this definition for their 'criticality ratio' - the ratio of water withdrawals for human use to total renewable water resources. The limitations of the criticality ratio and similar indicators are the following: the data on water resources availability do not take into account how much of it could be made available for human use; the water withdrawal data do not take into account how much of it is consumptively used (or evapotranspired) and how much could be available for recycling, through return flows; and the indicators do not take into account a society's adaptive capacity to cope with stress (Rijsberman, 2006).

Water Poverty Index (WPI)

The Water Poverty Index (WPI) has been conceived as the all-inclusive holistic index that wants to overcome all the drawbacks of WSI. The index aggregates components in five dimensions: access to water; water quantity, quality, and variability; water uses for domestic, food and productive purposes; capacity for water management; and environmental aspects. This index has the advantage of its comprehensiveness, but it is hampered by its complexity and lack of intuitive understanding, as with all similar indices (Rijsberman, 2006).